

Forest Science

Accuracy of whitebark pine and limber pine identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis field crews --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	FS-2024-058R1
Full Title:	Accuracy of whitebark pine and limber pine identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis field crews
Article Type:	Research Article
Keywords:	Forest inventory; genetic identification; whitebark pine; limber pine; quality assessment
Corresponding Author:	Shayla Williams, B.A. USDA Forest Service Rocky Mountain Research Station Grangeville, ID UNITED STATES
Corresponding Author's Institution:	USDA Forest Service Rocky Mountain Research Station
First Author:	Shayla Williams
First Author Secondary Information:	
Order of Authors:	Shayla Williams James E. Steed Jeremy Morrone Sara A. Goeking Matt Lavin Erich Kyle Dodson Rachel E. Simons
Order of Authors Secondary Information:	
Manuscript Region of Origin:	UNITED STATES
Abstract:	Accurate identification of whitebark and limber pine has become increasingly important following the 2022 listing of whitebark pine as a threatened species under the Endangered Species Act. However, morphological similarities make identification of the two species difficult where ranges overlap. Using a genetic test that differentiates whitebark and limber pine, we compared field identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis field crews with genetic identification for needle samples from 371 trees. Field identifications were 100% correct for the 76 samples collected from outside regions of species' range overlap. Eighty-three percent of the field identifications were correct in regions of range overlap (89% for large trees, 88% for saplings, and 78% for seedlings). Field-identified samples were correct 60% of the time for limber pine and >99% for whitebark pine. Random forests analysis revealed that identification accuracy is influenced by crew experience, large (≥ 12.7 cm diameter) limber or whitebark pines recorded by field crews on the plot, elevation, Julian day of sample collection, and habitat type. We found that whitebark pine has likely been underestimated, and limber pine overestimated, within their overlapping ranges. We provide insights on improving accuracy of future monitoring where these species overlap.
Suggested Reviewers:	Diana F. Tomback, Ph.D. Professor, University of Colorado Denver College of Liberal Arts and Sciences diana.tomback@ucdenver.edu Diana Tomback is a leading researcher on the ecology, conservation, and restoration of five-needle white pines in western North America. Elizabeth Pansing, Ph.D. Director, Forest and Restoration Science, American Forests Inc epansing@americanforests.org Elizabeth Pansing has researched whitebark pine ecology and management as well as

	<p>alpine and subalpine forests and she has used FIA data for whitebark pine modeling.</p> <p>Melissa Jenkins Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation melissa.jenkins@whitebarkfound.org Melissa Jenkins is experienced in whitebark pine silviculture, management, and recovery.</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Author response to comments</p> <p>We thank the Editor, Associate Editor, and Reviewers for their helpful comments, which allowed us to substantively improve this manuscript. We have reorganized the previously combined Results/Discussion section to include separate results and discussion, with a subsection for “Implications for users of FIA data” and a concise “Conclusions” subsection in the discussion. We also incorporated changes to address each specific comment, as described below. Each Editor/Reviewer comment is listed followed by our response with updated line numbers.</p> <p>Comments from the Editors and Reviewers:</p> <p>Editor in chief:</p> <p>The suggested revisions are a bit more extensive than I typically allow for this decision, so I gave you an extra 10 days to address them. Reviewer 2 does suggest separating the results and discussion into two sections; if you take that route, please have the "Conclusions" as a subsection within the discussion (the suggested title "Management Implications" is fine).</p> <p>Response: Thank you for the additional time and for providing clarity on the recommendation to separate results and discussion. We have reorganized the paper as suggested, and we agree that this flow and organization is improved.</p> <p>For Table 2, I would prefer a setup more aligned with a traditional table. You could display most of that information in 7 columns; as long as provide the total sample size, I think the actual confusion matrix can be calculated from the 5 summary metrics you already provide.</p> <p>Response: We appreciate this suggestion for improved presentation clarity and have modified the format of Table 2 as suggested.</p> <p>Associate Editor:</p> <p>The paper is refreshingly well-written with a clear purpose, appropriate methods, and well reasoned conclusions. The reviewers have made some suggestions for further improvement, which I recommend the authors consider before finalizing the paper. Some minor editorial suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - insert a space between values and units (e.g., "2100m" line 351 and elsewhere) <p>Response: Thank you for noting the strengths of the paper as well as the need to properly space values relative to units. We have made this change throughout the manuscript.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - figure captions seem very long. is it possible to condense? <p>Response: We condensed the captions and took out some redundancy in the alternative text (e.g. restating of results and methods that are discussed in the manuscript).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - is there room to insert a map of the USA to indicate the position of the study area within the country? For. Sci. is an international journal, and we should do our best to make this clear in illustrations. <p>Response: We have added a location map of North America that highlights the Rocky Mountain Research Station and our study area (see Figure 1).</p>

Reviewer #1: This paper covers an important topic. It is well-structured and easy to follow.
The problem and objectives are well-stated.
I find that the methodology used responds to the objectives of the analysis.
The results and discussion are clear and answer the questions and hypothesis of the study.

Response: Thank you for taking the time to review the manuscript and provide this positive feedback.

Reviewer #2:

The paper investigates how well FIA field crews are able to differentiate whitebark pine and limber pine, which are similar in needle and tree growth form characteristics and overlap in elevation and some site types. The study focuses on FIA plot locations where whitebark pine and limber pine overlap in the Rocky Mountains. It takes advantage of five-needle pine needle tissue collections from FIA plots, originally intended for other purposes, which were then genetically analyzed comparing two different chloroplast loci which can conclusively distinguish whitebark and limber pine. Correctly identifying whitebark pine to determine where it occurs has become particularly important since its federal listing as a threatened species was announced in 2022 (but effective in 2023). The listing has increased interest in the species and various modeling efforts, particularly with respect to climate change and the impact of several threats.

In general, the paper is an important contribution to a very focused area of concern. The authors have conducted a thorough analysis of the frequency of misclassification of both pines in the FIA database and also examine correlates of successful classification. They use several statistical approaches to examine mis-classification, including developing confusion matrices from the FIA data and analysis results, identifying potential predictors of misclassification, and then applying a random forests model to determine important indicators.

The paper and analyses are well-devised and take advantage of fortuitously useful data; however, the data analyses are based on a comparatively small sample size for the scope of the analyses. The number of needle samples per FIA plot depended on whether crews thought they had one or two five-needle white pines, which is a sampling limitation. The results also under-estimate the occurrence of whitebark pine in FIA plots, but the authors are clear on this point. Another concern that could be mentioned in the discussion: although the ranges of whitebark pine and limber are examined in this paper in order to identify the area of overlap, including a large buffer zone, the distribution of limber pine in some regions, and even whitebark pine, remain incompletely known potentially even in the study region and there may be unknown overlap. Consequently, FIA crews could potentially mis-identify seedlings outside the identified overlap zone. As examples but outside the Rocky Mountains region of interest, a new small population of whitebark pine was discovered (in Olympic National Park) and populations of limber pine in southern British Columbia within the last decade or so.

Response: These are important points that we attempted to be more transparent about in the revised manuscript. In the Discussion, we acknowledge that verifying the true range of these species' overlap would require a much larger sample size than we used in this analysis (see L494-497).

The structure of the paper is a little unusual in that results and discussion are combined. In order to emphasize the critical points, I would suggest a "General Discussion" section instead of "Implications for users of FIA data" that encompasses some individual points brought up and then a concluding "Management Implications" section rather than a "Conclusions" section, which includes the material currently in "Conclusions" but may expand and bring additional points in. The identification issue is not just a problem for FIA data but for survey and monitoring purposes and especially for determining distributional data. Also, problems with identification may occur for FIA and monitoring data in other areas of overlap between species of five-needle white pines especially for distinguishing pre-reproductive age classes, e.g., including western white pine and whitebark pine, although the needle traits are a little more distinctive but

not always clear. This analysis and concern about data quality thus have implications beyond the single issue of distinguishing non-reproductive whitebark and limber pine.

Response: We appreciate the suggestion to reorganize the paper with separate Results and Discussion sections, and we have made this change. Additionally, we added language to the Conclusions to highlight that our findings may be useful not just for FIA data collection but for any studies that rely on field-based species identification (L489-490, L423-425).

It is important to mention early in the introduction that seeds of both trees are primarily disseminated by Clark's nutcracker but fallen limber pine seeds may be cached locally by small mammals and jays. Nutcracker caches of both pine species may be raided by granivorous rodents (e.g., Pansing et al. 2017) and secondarily cached. Nutcrackers will cache seeds only a few meters from source trees as well as flying seeds to a max of 32 km (Tomback 1978, Lorenz et al. 2011). The implications of nutcracker seed dispersal (e.g., Tomback et al. 2011) is that the bird can disseminate seeds far from seed sources and in different forest types which Goeking et al. (2019) confirmed using FIA data. This perspective may have bearing on the challenges posed by five-needle pine identification. The section beginning L33 is confusing to a reader who is not aware of this information.

Response: Thank you for this helpful information about dispersers and how their different dispersal characteristics affect the distribution of these tree species. We have revised this paragraph to incorporate the information you shared (see L33-43).

Regarding Table 3 results, L204 in the Methods does not explain the use of Chi-square in Cramer's V scores, with which many readers may be unfamiliar.

Citation/explanation? The caption for Table 3 alludes to it. This needs to be better addressed in both places.

Response: We added a brief explanation of Cramer's V scores as an indication of the strength of relationships among two categorical variables such as when using chi-square tests (see L214-215 and Table 3).

There are alternative legends presented for the figures and tables. Some are very long with shorter alternative versions. If more information were in the text, the legends could state "see text for details."

Response: We have shortened the figure legends and alternative text. We aimed to reduce redundancy between manuscript and the figure legends and alternative text. We maintained informative alternate text for readers who may not be able to visually interpret information presented solely in the figures.

The paper in general is generally well-written, but there are a number of places where alternative wording would clarify a statement or procedure, and some of the methods presented are confusing. For example, under Materials and Methods, the needle sampling protocol, i.e., how many samples per plot and how selected, needs to be clearer. They are listed below.

Response: Thank you for your attention to clarity. We have implemented each of your helpful suggestions, as described below.

Abstract

L3. Rather than "vegetative similarities," try morphological similarities. Vegetative preferred definition is plant growth.

Response: We appreciate this suggestion and have made this change (see Abstract, L3).

Study Implications: Please modify the last sentence. "These results demonstrate reliability of FIA for whitebark pine assessment...." The authors use reliability here as a qualitative measure but the casual reader may interpret the sentence as "the data are reliable."

Response: We revised this to "These results quantify reliability..." (see Study Implications, L7-8)

Introduction

L9-19, "decline" is used 6 times in this paragraph and needs alternative wording. Try L11 "...with higher rates of loss in recent years..." Try L16, "Because of these on-going threats...", or something similar.

Response: Thank you for pointing out this redundancy. We incorporated the suggested changes and reduced the use of 'decline' to two times in this paragraph (see L9-19).

L21, "However, the similarity..use between not of...."

Response: We have made this change (see L21).

L22, instead of "overall morphology," use growth form.

Response: We have made this change (see L22).

L 25, not "structure" but morphology.

Response: We have made this change (see L25).

L27-28, instead of "branch dieback"—not clear: use branch death or canopy kill.

Response: We have clarified that 'dieback' means 'branch death' (see L27-28).

L33-45, this paragraph needs work and more clarity. Nutcrackers are the dispersal agent likely to bring limber and whitebark pine seeds into disturbed areas. As a caveat, nutcrackers will cache seeds near seed source trees and also transport seeds several to many kilometers for seed caching.

Rodents occupy territories and would not range very far outside to gather cones. This sentence needs work—my edits: "The challenge of identifying young trees is exacerbated in disturbed areas, where both tree species may be pioneering, and in other forest types without five-needle white pines in the overstory." In both situations, long-distance seed dispersal by Clark's nutcrackers may lead to whitebark pine or limber pine regeneration in these community types if conditions are suitable.

Not sure which "other dispersal agents" the authors are referencing in the paragraph; none transport seeds over large distances, but rodents can locally re-cache seeds originally cached by nutcrackers and other rodents. Stellar's jays are territorial and do not transport more than a few seeds at a time and not over long distances. The authors should specifically mention findings in the Goeking et al. (2019) paper which also uses FIA data to make their point about whitebark pine regeneration in different forest communities.

Response: Thank you for your feedback and suggestions throughout this paragraph, and particularly the important contextual information about the various disperser species. To address these comments, we implemented the wording you kindly suggested. Additionally, we have made the following changes: First, we added 'up to' ('...typically disperse seeds up to a few kilometers away') to address that seeds are often cached near seed source trees (see L38). Second, we incorporated the suggested changes in lines 33-36 (now L34-37). Third, we removed the reference to 'other dispersal agents'. We also referenced the findings of Goeking et al. (2019) and other papers using FIA data to reach the same conclusion (see L42-43).

L44, Papers that demonstrate overlap at high elevations between whitebark and limber pine in the Rocky Mountains: Resler and Tomback (2008), AAAR and Tomback et al. (2014), AAAR. Referencing "the species" in this paragraph became confusing—maybe call out whitebark pine and limber pine here.

Response: We clarified statements that referred to one or both species throughout this paragraph. Thank you for the additional citations; we have revised the citations for this

statement (see L46-47).

L48, plots actually moved? Or relocated or established?

Response: Thank you for pointing the ambiguity of our original language. The guidance in the cited protocol states that if "...you cannot, with 100% confidence, verify which trees on the plot are whitebark, select an alternate plot from the list provided to sample." We have adjusted our wording to better reflect the language in the protocol (see L50-51).

L49-54, First, in reality up to Alongi et al. (2019), no reliable method was available for telling pre-reproductive age classes of whitebark and limber pine apart. Second, as implied, the importance of distinguishing whitebark and limber pine apart for every age class varies with the objectives of the monitoring or survey. If not distributional than not as critical. Resler and Tomback (2008) applied the needle morphology differences noted by Kral, R. (1993) (Pinus. In Flora of North America Editorial Committee, 1993, Flora of North America North of Mexico, Vol. 2. New York and Oxford: Oxford University Press) which seemed to work sufficiently in their study area (but no control) but requires hand lens or dissecting microscope and specific knowledge.

Response: Thank you for drawing attention to this paragraph. We were not intending to disparage any of the described methodologies, as they were designed to meet study objectives and use available resources. We have added some additional text to this paragraph to acknowledge the utility of these methods while also explaining why incorporating new resources (the test detailed in Alongi et al. 2019) is necessary for the type of sample design used by FIA (see L56-60). Additionally, we have referenced the methodology used by Resler and Tomback (2008) (see L55-56).

L95, 97, "approximately" implies nearly equal to. Is another term better to use here?

Response: In the first instance, we use "approximately" (now L101) because although this seems to be an exact number, some plots represent more or less area, based on FIA estimation procedures or plot placement (e.g., plots that land on the edge of the RMRS region). We did not include this level of detail, though specifics can be found in the cited references. In the second instance, we removed the word "approximately" because we do aim to sample exactly 10% of plots each year. The actual percentage varies due to circumstances that may temporarily prevent plot measurement (e.g. pandemic related travel restrictions). To account for this, we have clarified that 10% of FIA plots 'are targeted' for visit each year (see L103-104).

L99, what is the FIA plot size or range of sizes?

Response: Plot size is always the same. We now report the size to the nearest square meter (see L105).

L100, need spaces around symbols \geq and units of measurement. Where is the diameter measured? Is it DBH?

L102, DBH? clarify diameter limits and where measured.

Response: Thank you for drawing our attention to this formatting. We have fixed the symbol and unit spacing throughout the document. We now refer to 'diameter' throughout the paragraph because we are referencing the FIA protocol, which pertains to species that have diameters measured at breast height and root collar (L105-111). We added a sentence at the end of the paragraph to clarify that diameter is taken at breast height for whitebark and limber pine (see L109-111).

L105-111. The sampling protocol is confusing. You start out stating "one tissue sample consisting of at least five needles from one individual..." Can you clarify the decision flow of how many sample to collect, and how many needle samples and how distributed among plots, subplots etc.?

Response: Thank you for pointing out where we need to clarify our protocol. We have revised both individual sentences and the order of statements in the paragraph to provide a clearer description (see L113-122).

L114-115, "conclusively identified" through the genetic methods? Please provide information.

Response: We clarified that these samples had conclusive genetic test results (i.e. DNA successfully extracted, no contamination, etc.) (see L123).

L154, define "false positive error rates."

Response: We provide a citation (James et al. 2013), a formula, and a narrative description of false positive error rates in the text immediately following the formula (see L162, L164, and L167-168).

L167-175. Why is Table 3 cited after Table 1? Unless I missed something, Table 3 should be converted to Table 2.

Response: Thank you for noticing this. We have modified the text to refer to Table 3 in the Results, after Table 2 is introduced, and edited the Methods to not refer to Table 3.

L198-199, "how misidentifications may affect occurrence patterns..." It strikes me that this is a derivative piece of information. The predictor variables and modelling indicate which factors are more likely to lead to misidentifications.

Response: Thank you for noticing this ambiguous word choice. We changed this sentence to "We compared field- versus lab-identified whitebark pine presence across different predictor variable values or categories to better understand the circumstances in which misidentification is most likely to occur." (see L208-210).

L208-209. This needs be rewritten. It is accuracy that comes from cumulative experience; "cumulative accuracy" is not a good descriptor for this situation.

Response: Thank you for careful consideration of our word choice. Rather than changing the descriptor, we clarified the definition of "cumulative accuracy," because it does indeed refer to the mean accuracy of all samples collected by a crew leader over time. For example, if a crew leader collected one sample and incorrectly identified it on their first plot, they would have a cumulative accuracy of 0% (0 out of 1 samples correctly identified). If they correctly identified 2 samples on their second plot, their cumulative accuracy would increase to 67% (2 out of 3 samples correctly identified). We hope this methodology is now sufficiently clear in the manuscript and reflects the example provided here. Please see L220-221 (Methods) and L268-269 (Results).

Results

L219, Table 2 should be renamed Table 3 because of the order of reference (see above).

Response: We removed the earlier reference to Table 3, as that reference did not add substantive value to the Methods section. Thus, the original table numbering has not changed, and the order of reference matches the numbering.

L221-225. The explanation differentiating seed dispersal by nutcrackers in whitebark pine and limber pine is very speculative and should be eliminated. Limber pine seeds are often dispersed long distances by nutcrackers (Lanner and Vander Wall 1980, Williams et al. 2020). I would focus on the fact that the whitebark pine cones are less persistent on trees because they are deconstructed in the process of seed removal, but we often find remnants of previous years' cones on whitebark pine trees—to the point they confuse novices about new cones when we do cone counts. Limber pine may have several years' of old cones remaining on trees, which in fact makes it easier to assign tree identity.

Response: Thank you for drawing attention to this. We removed the speculative explanation and focused on the effects of cone persistence (see L342-351).

L243-248, this explanation might be better served where the two models are described

under Methods.

Response: We moved this explanation to the Methods section (see new location at L202-206, and L243-245).

L249-260. Should probably refer back to Table 1 again for the factors listed.

Response: Thank you for noting this linkage. We added a reference to Table 1 (see L235-236, L248).

L283, not "between" but among (3 or more).

Response: We have made this change (see L278).

L285-289, see comments above about Chi-square (sometimes capitalized in paper, sometimes not) and Cramer's V scores.

Response: We have revised all occurrence of chi-square to be lower case. Additionally, we added an explanation of Cramer's V scores, their relation to chi-square tests (see L214-216).

L293, "often leaving no evidence of cones afterward..." I would state small remnants or no evidence.

Response: We have made this change (see L346).

L334, Indent, new paragraph.

Response: We have created a separate paragraph to discuss the relationship of habitat type and five-needle pines (L308-319). With the reorganization of results and discussion, the suggested paragraph break is now the second sentence of the paragraph (L310).

L 356, "...shift in limber pine elevation suggests..." not means.

Response: Thank you for your attention to this language. We have made this change (see L326).

L382-383, this sentence is not clear. Please state more simply—it is important.

Response: We have revised this sentence and also moved it to the end of the paragraph to better indicate that these FIA-specific error rates likely extend beyond our results to other monitoring datasets (see L423-425).

L436, clarify writing--not "contain" but include only...

Response: We have made this change (see L473).

L453, clarify this suggestion: "First, sample protocols can target..." Should prioritize?

Response: We agree "should prioritize" is clearer and made this change (see L490-491).

L457, rewrite: "targeted training" not clear. Training that emphasizes distinguishing whitebark pine from limber pine...?

Response: We revised these sentences to add some clarity to the purpose and content of suggested training, and remove the phrase 'targeted training' (see L497-L502).

L452-462, Rolling in all these factors such as forest type and habitat type, etc. may help improve accuracy. This would be worth studying. The only definitive approach is to use the genetic method.

Response: We clarified that crews should be trained to rely on these factors for

	<p>identification only when verification via other methods (i.e. cones, genetic analysis) is not possible (see L497-L500). We agree that studying the effects of training on accuracy would be valuable, and more genetic sampling by trained employees is necessary to do so (see L503-506).</p> <p>L463-467, more accuracy in distinguishing the two species is also important for any modelling regarding seedling niches or climate change predictions.</p> <p>Response: Thank you for drawing our attention to this area, as our original phrasing obscured the paragraph topic. This paragraph was intended to focus on the relationship between genetic sampling and training, specifically how improved understanding of occurrence could improve field identification (which, as mentioned in the previous comment, will be worth studying as data becomes available). The benefits of more accurate identification are numerous, and we have tried to address them throughout the paper. We have re-written this section to clarify the focus (see L503-506), and we specifically mention the benefits for seedling niche and climate change projections in lines 509-511.</p> <p>L486, instead of targeted training, which is jargony, it would be more details training that integrates multiple factors to distinguish between the species.</p> <p>Response: Thank you for this suggestion. We have changed this sentence to read '...crews that are trained to use multiple factors for species identification' (see L529).</p>				
Additional Information:					
Question	Response				
Please enter the Word Count of your manuscript	7604				
How many figures are included in your manuscript? (Exclude supplementary materials.)	4				
Manuscript Classifications:	genetics; inventory planning; inventory statistics; monitoring; national forest inventory				
Corresponding Author E-Mail:	shayla.williams@usda.gov				
Funding Information:	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Rocky Mountain Research Station</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Montana State University</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	Rocky Mountain Research Station	Not applicable	Montana State University	Not applicable
Rocky Mountain Research Station	Not applicable				
Montana State University	Not applicable				
Section/Category:	Forest Management				

Author response to comments

We thank the Editor, Associate Editor, and Reviewers for their helpful comments, which allowed us to substantively improve this manuscript. We have reorganized the previously combined Results/Discussion section to include separate results and discussion, with a subsection for “Implications for users of FIA data” and a concise “Conclusions” subsection in the discussion. We also incorporated changes to address each specific comment, as described below. Each Editor/Reviewer comment is listed followed by our italicized response with updated line numbers.

Comments from the Editors and Reviewers:

Editor in chief:

The suggested revisions are a bit more extensive than I typically allow for this decision, so I gave you an extra 10 days to address them. Reviewer 2 does suggest separating the results and discussion into two sections; if you take that route, please have the "Conclusions" as a subsection within the discussion (the suggested title "Management Implications" is fine).

Response: Thank you for the additional time and for providing clarity on the recommendation to separate results and discussion. We have reorganized the paper as suggested, and we agree that this flow and organization is improved.

For Table 2, I would prefer a setup more aligned with a traditional table. You could display most of that information in 7 columns; as long as provide the total sample size, I think the actual confusion matrix can be calculated from the 5 summary metrics you already provide.

Response: We appreciate this suggestion for improved presentation clarity and have modified the format of Table 2 as suggested.

Associate Editor:

The paper is refreshingly well-written with a clear purpose, appropriate methods, and well reasoned conclusions. The reviewers have made some suggestions for further improvement, which I recommend the authors consider before finalizing the paper. Some minor editorial suggestions:

- insert a space between values and units (e.g., "2100m" line 351 and elsewhere)

Response: Thank you for noting the strengths of the paper as well as the need to properly space values relative to units. We have made this change throughout the manuscript.

- figure captions seem very long. is it possible to condense?

Response: We condensed the captions and took out some redundancy in the alternative text (e.g. restating of results and methods that are discussed in the manuscript).

- is there room to insert a map of the USA to indicate the position of the study area within the country? For. Sci. is an international journal, and we should do our best to make this clear in illustrations.

Response: We have added a location map of North America that highlights the Rocky Mountain Research Station and our study area (see Figure 1).

Reviewer #1: This paper covers an important topic. It is well-structured and easy to follow. The problem and objectives are well-stated. I find that the methodology used responds to the objectives of the analysis. The results and discussion are clear and answer the questions and hypothesis of the study.

Response: Thank you for taking the time to review the manuscript and provide this positive feedback.

Reviewer #2:

The paper investigates how well FIA field crews are able to differentiate whitebark pine and limber pine, which are similar in needle and tree growth form characteristics and overlap in elevation and some site types. The study focuses on FIA plot locations where whitebark pine and limber pine overlap in the Rocky Mountains. It takes advantage of five-needle pine needle tissue collections from FIA plots, originally intended for other purposes, which were then genetically analyzed comparing two different chloroplast loci which can conclusively distinguish whitebark and limber pine. Correctly identifying whitebark pine to determine where it occurs has become particularly important since its federal listing as a threatened species was announced in 2022 (but effective in 2023). The listing has increased interest in the species and various modeling efforts, particularly with respect to climate change and the impact of several threats.

In general, the paper is an important contribution to a very focused area of concern. The authors have conducted a thorough analysis of the frequency of misclassification of both pines in the FIA database and also examine correlates of successful classification. They use several statistical approaches to examine mis-classification, including developing confusion matrices from the FIA data and analysis results, identifying potential predictors of misclassification, and then applying a random forests model to determine important indicators.

The paper and analyses are well-devised and take advantage of fortuitously useful data; however, the data analyses are based on a comparatively small sample size for the scope of the analyses. The number of needle samples per FIA plot depended on whether crews thought they had one or two five-needle white pines, which is a sampling limitation. The results also under-estimate the occurrence of whitebark pine in FIA plots, but the authors are clear on this point. Another concern that could be mentioned in the discussion: although the ranges of whitebark pine and limber are examined in this paper in order to identify the area of overlap, including a large buffer zone, the distribution of limber pine in some regions, and even whitebark pine, remain incompletely known potentially even in the study region and there may be unknown overlap. Consequently, FIA crews could potentially mis-identify seedlings outside the identified overlap zone. As examples but outside the Rocky Mountains region of interest, a new small population of whitebark pine was discovered (in Olympic National Park) and populations of limber pine in southern British Columbia within the last decade or so.

Response: These are important points that we attempted to be more transparent about in the revised manuscript. In the Discussion, we acknowledge that verifying the true range of these species' overlap would require a much larger sample size than we used in this analysis (see L494-497).

The structure of the paper is a little unusual in that results and discussion are combined. In order to emphasize the critical points, I would suggest a "General Discussion" section instead of "Implications for users of FIA data" that encompasses some individual points brought up and then a concluding "Management Implications" section rather than a "Conclusions" section, which includes the material currently in "Conclusions" but may expand and bring additional points in. The identification issue is not

just a problem for FIA data but for survey and monitoring purposes and especially for determining distributional data. Also, problems with identification may occur for FIA and monitoring data in other areas of overlap between species of five-needle white pines especially for distinguishing pre-reproductive age classes, e.g., including western white pine and whitebark pine, although the needle traits are a little more distinctive but not always clear. This analysis and concern about data quality thus have implications beyond the single issue of distinguishing non-reproductive whitebark and limber pine.

Response: We appreciate the suggestion to reorganize the paper with separate Results and Discussion sections, and we have made this change. Additionally, we added language to the Conclusions to highlight that our findings may be useful not just for FIA data collection but for any studies that rely on field-based species identification (L489-490, L423-425).

It is important to mention early in the introduction that seeds of both trees are primarily disseminated by Clark's nutcracker but fallen limber pine seeds may be cached locally by small mammals and jays. Nutcracker caches of both pine species may be raided by granivorous rodents (e.g., Pansing et al. 2017) and secondarily cached. Nutcrackers will cache seeds only a few meters from source trees as well as flying seeds to a max of 32 km (Tomback 1978, Lorenz et al. 2011). The implications of nutcracker seed dispersal (e.g., Tomback et al. 2011) is that the bird can disseminate seeds far from seed sources and in different forest types which Goeking et al. (2019) confirmed using FIA data. This perspective may have bearing on the challenges posed by five-needle pine identification. The section beginning L33 is confusing to a reader who is not aware of this information.

Response: Thank you for this helpful information about dispersers and how their different dispersal characteristics affect the distribution of these tree species. We have revised this paragraph to incorporate the information you shared (see L33-43).

Regarding Table 3 results, L204 in the Methods does not explain the use of Chi-square in Cramer's V scores, with which many readers may be unfamiliar. Citation/explanation? The caption for Table 3 alludes to it. This needs to be better addressed in both places.

Response: We added a brief explanation of Cramer's V scores as an indication of the strength of relationships among two categorical variables such as when using chi-square tests (see L214-215 and Table 3).

There are alternative legends presented for the figures and tables. Some are very long with shorter alternative versions. If more information were in the text, the legends could state "see text for details."

Response: We have shortened the figure legends and alternative text. We aimed to reduce redundancy between manuscript and the figure legends and alternative text. We maintained informative alternate text for readers who may not be able to visually interpret information presented solely in the figures.

The paper in general is generally well-written, but there are a number of places where alternative wording would clarify a statement or procedure, and some of the methods presented are confusing. For example, under Materials and Methods, the needle sampling protocol, i.e., how many samples per plot and how selected, needs to be clearer. They are listed below.

Response: Thank you for your attention to clarity. We have implemented each of your helpful suggestions, as described below.

Abstract

L3. Rather than "vegetative similarities," try morphological similarities. Vegetative preferred definition is plant growth.

Response: We appreciate this suggestion and have made this change (see Abstract, L3).

Study Implications: Please modify the last sentence. "These results demonstrate reliability of FIA for whitebark pine assessment...." The authors use reliability here as a qualitative measure but the casual reader may interpret the sentence as "the data are reliable."

Response: We revised this to "These results quantify reliability..." (see Study Implications, L7-8)

Introduction

L9-19, "decline" is used 6 times in this paragraph and needs alternative wording. Try L11 "...with higher rates of loss in recent years..." Try L16, "Because of these on-going threats...", or something similar.

Response: Thank you for pointing out this redundancy. We incorporated the suggested changes and reduced the use of 'decline' to two times in this paragraph (see L9-19).

L21, "However, the similarity..use between not of...."

Response: We have made this change (see L21).

L22, instead of "overall morphology," use growth form.

Response: We have made this change (see L22).

L 25, not "structure" but morphology.

Response: We have made this change (see L25).

L27-28, instead of "branch dieback"—not clear: use branch death or canopy kill.

Response: We have clarified that 'dieback' means 'branch death' (see L27-28).

L33-45, this paragraph needs work and more clarity. Nutcrackers are the dispersal agent likely to bring limber and whitebark pine seeds into disturbed areas. As a caveat, nutcrackers will cache seeds near seed source trees and also transport seeds several to many kilometers for seed caching.

Rodents occupy territories and would not range very far outside to gather cones. This sentence needs work—my edits: "The challenge of identifying young trees is exacerbated in disturbed areas, where both tree species may be pioneering, and in other forest types without five-needle white pines in the overstory." In both situations, long-distance seed dispersal by Clark's nutcrackers may lead to whitebark pine or limber pine regeneration in these community types if conditions are suitable.

Not sure which "other dispersal agents" the authors are referencing in the paragraph; none transport seeds over large distances, but rodents can locally re-cache seeds originally cached by nutcrackers and

other rodents. Stellar's jays are territorial and do not transport more than a few seeds at a time and not over long distances. The authors should specifically mention findings in the Goeking et al. (2019) paper which also uses FIA data to make their point about whitebark pine regeneration in different forest communities.

Response: Thank you for your feedback and suggestions throughout this paragraph, and particularly the important contextual information about the various disperser species. To address these comments, we implemented the wording you kindly suggested. Additionally, we have made the following changes: First, we added 'up to' ('...typically disperse seeds up to a few kilometers away') to address that seeds are often cached near seed source trees (see L38). Second, we incorporated the suggested changes in lines 33-36 (now L34-37). Third, we removed the reference to 'other dispersal agents'. We also referenced the findings of Goeking et al. (2019) and other papers using FIA data to reach the same conclusion (see L42-43).

L44, Papers that demonstrate overlap at high elevations between whitebark and limber pine in the Rocky Mountains: Resler and Tomback (2008), AAAR and Tomback et al. (2014), AAAR. Referencing "the species" in this paragraph became confusing—maybe call out whitebark pine and limber pine here.

Response: We clarified statements that referred to one or both species throughout this paragraph. Thank you for the additional citations; we have revised the citations for this statement (see L46-47).

L48, plots actually moved? Or relocated or established?

Response: Thank you for pointing the ambiguity of our original language. The guidance in the cited protocol states that if "...you cannot, with 100% confidence, verify which trees on the plot are whitebark, select an alternate plot from the list provided to sample." We have adjusted our wording to better reflect the language in the protocol (see L50-51).

L49-54, First, in reality up to Alongi et al. (2019), no reliable method was available for telling pre-reproductive age classes of whitebark and limber pine apart. Second, as implied, the importance of distinguishing whitebark and limber pine apart for every age class varies with the objectives of the monitoring or survey. If not distributional than not as critical. Resler and Tomback (2008) applied the needle morphology differences noted by Kral, R. (1993) (Pinus. In Flora of North America Editorial Committee, 1993, Flora of North America North of Mexico, Vol. 2. New York and Oxford: Oxford University Press) which seemed to work sufficiently in their study area (but no control) but requires hand lens or dissecting microscope and specific knowledge.

Response: Thank you for drawing attention to this paragraph. We were not intending to disparage any of the described methodologies, as they were designed to meet study objectives and use available resources. We have added some additional text to this paragraph to acknowledge the utility of these methods while also explaining why incorporating new resources (the test detailed in Alongi et al. 2019) is necessary for the type of sample design used by FIA (see L56-60). Additionally, we have referenced the methodology used by Resler and Tomback (2008) (see L55-56).

L95, 97, "approximately" implies nearly equal to. Is another term better to use here?

Response: In the first instance, we use "approximately" (now L101) because although this seems to be an exact number, some plots represent more or less area, based on FIA estimation procedures or plot

placement (e.g., plots that land on the edge of the RMRS region). We did not include this level of detail, though specifics can be found in the cited references. In the second instance, we removed the word "approximately" because we do aim to sample exactly 10% of plots each year. The actual percentage varies due to circumstances that may temporarily prevent plot measurement (e.g. pandemic related travel restrictions). To account for this, we have clarified that 10% of FIA plots 'are targeted' for visit each year (see L103-104).

L99, what is the FIA plot size or range of sizes?

Response: Plot size is always the same. We now report the size to the nearest square meter (see L105).

L100, need spaces around symbols \geq and units of measurement. Where is the diameter measured? Is it DBH?

L102, DBH? clarify diameter limits and where measured.

Response: Thank you for drawing our attention to this formatting. We have fixed the symbol and unit spacing throughout the document. We now refer to 'diameter' throughout the paragraph because we are referencing the FIA protocol, which pertains to species that have diameters measured at breast height and root collar (L105-111). We added a sentence at the end of the paragraph to clarify that diameter is taken at breast height for whitebark and limber pine (see L109-111).

L105-111. The sampling protocol is confusing. You start out stating "one tissue sample consisting of at least five needles from one individual..." Can you clarify the decision flow of how many sample to collect, and how many needle samples and how distributed among plots, subplots etc.?

Response: Thank you for pointing out where we need to clarify our protocol. We have revised both individual sentences and the order of statements in the paragraph to provide a clearer description (see L113-122).

L114-115, "conclusively identified" through the genetic methods? Please provide information.

Response: We clarified that these samples had conclusive genetic test results (i.e. DNA successfully extracted, no contamination, etc.) (see L123).

L154, define "false positive error rates."

Response: We provide a citation (James et al. 2013), a formula, and a narrative description of false positive error rates in the text immediately following the formula (see L162, L164, and L167-168).

L167-175. Why is Table 3 cited after Table 1? Unless I missed something, Table 3 should be converted to Table 2.

Response: Thank you for noticing this. We have modified the text to refer to Table 3 in the Results, after Table 2 is introduced, and edited the Methods to not refer to Table 3.

L198-199, "how misidentifications may affect occurrence patterns..." It strikes me that this is a derivative piece of information. The predictor variables and modelling indicate which factors are more likely to lead to misidentifications.

Response: Thank you for noticing this ambiguous word choice. We changed this sentence to "We compared field- versus lab-identified whitebark pine presence across different predictor variable values or categories to better understand the circumstances in which misidentification is most likely to occur." (see L208-210).

L208-209. This needs to be rewritten. It is accuracy that comes from cumulative experience; "cumulative accuracy" is not a good descriptor for this situation.

Response: Thank you for careful consideration of our word choice. Rather than changing the descriptor, we clarified the definition of "cumulative accuracy," because it does indeed refer to the mean accuracy of all samples collected by a crew leader over time. For example, if a crew leader collected one sample and incorrectly identified it on their first plot, they would have a cumulative accuracy of 0% (0 out of 1 samples correctly identified). If they correctly identified 2 samples on their second plot, their cumulative accuracy would increase to 67% (2 out of 3 samples correctly identified). We hope this methodology is now sufficiently clear in the manuscript and reflects the example provided here. Please see L220-221 (Methods) and L268-269 (Results).

Results

L219, Table 2 should be renamed Table 3 because of the order of reference (see above).

Response: We removed the earlier reference to Table 3, as that reference did not add substantive value to the Methods section. Thus, the original table numbering has not changed, and the order of reference matches the numbering.

L221-225. The explanation differentiating seed dispersal by nutcrackers in whitebark pine and limber pine is very speculative and should be eliminated. Limber pine seeds are often dispersed long distances by nutcrackers (Lanner and Vander Wall 1980, Williams et al. 2020). I would focus on the fact that the whitebark pine cones are less persistent on trees because they are deconstructed in the process of seed removal, but we often find remnants of previous years' cones on whitebark pine trees—to the point they confuse novices about new cones when we do cone counts. Limber pine may have several years' of old cones remaining on trees, which in fact makes it easier to assign tree identity.

Response: Thank you for drawing attention to this. We removed the speculative explanation and focused on the effects of cone persistence (see L342-351).

L243-248, this explanation might be better served where the two models are described under Methods.

Response: We moved this explanation to the Methods section (see new location at L202-206, and L243-245).

L249-260. Should probably refer back to Table 1 again for the factors listed.

Response: Thank you for noting this linkage. We added a reference to Table 1 (see L235-236, L248).

L283, not "between" but among (3 or more).

Response: We have made this change (see L278).

L285-289, see comments above about Chi-square (sometimes capitalized in paper, sometimes not) and Cramer's V scores.

Response: We have revised all occurrence of chi-square to be lower case. Additionally, we added an explanation of Cramer's V scores, their relation to chi-square tests (see L214-216).

L293, "often leaving no evidence of cones afterward..." I would state small remnants or no evidence.

Response: We have made this change (see L346).

L334, Indent, new paragraph.

Response: We have created a separate paragraph to discuss the relationship of habitat type and five-needle pines (L308-319). With the reorganization of results and discussion, the suggested paragraph break is now the second sentence of the paragraph (L310).

L 356, "...shift in limber pine elevation suggests...." not means.

Response: Thank you for your attention to this language. We have made this change (see L326).

L382-383, this sentence is not clear. Please state more simply—it is important.

Response: We have revised this sentence and also moved it to the end of the paragraph to better indicate that these FIA-specific error rates likely extend beyond our results to other monitoring datasets (see L423-425).

L436, clarify writing--not "contain" but include only...

Response: We have made this change (see L473).

L453, clarify this suggestion: "First, sample protocols can target...." Should prioritize?

Response: We agree "should prioritize" is clearer and made this change (see L490-491).

L457, rewrite: "targeted training" not clear. Training that emphasizes distinguishing whitebark pine from limber pine...?

Response: We revised these sentences to add some clarity to the purpose and content of suggested training, and remove the phrase 'targeted training' (see L497-L502).

L452-462, Rolling in all these factors such as forest type and habitat type, etc. may help improve accuracy. This would be worth studying. The only definitive approach is to use the genetic method.

Response: We clarified that crews should be trained to rely on these factors for identification only when verification via other methods (i.e. cones, genetic analysis) is not possible (see L497-L500). We agree that

studying the effects of training on accuracy would be valuable, and more genetic sampling by trained employees is necessary to do so (see L503-506).

L463-467, more accuracy in distinguishing the two species is also important for any modelling regarding seedling niches or climate change predictions.

Response: Thank you for drawing our attention to this area, as our original phrasing obscured the paragraph topic. This paragraph was intended to focus on the relationship between genetic sampling and training, specifically how improved understanding of occurrence could improve field identification (which, as mentioned in the previous comment, will be worth studying as data becomes available). The benefits of more accurate identification are numerous, and we have tried to address them throughout the paper. We have re-written this section to clarify the focus (see L503-506), and we specifically mention the benefits for seedling niche and climate change projections in lines 509-511.

L486, instead of targeted training, which is jargony, it would be more details training that integrates multiple factors to distinguish between the species.

Response: Thank you for this suggestion. We have changed this sentence to read ‘...crews that are trained to use multiple factors for species identification’ (see L529).

Accuracy of whitebark pine and limber pine identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis field crews

Shayla R. Williams¹, James E. Steed², Jeremy Morrone³, Sara A. Goeking⁴, Matt Lavin⁵, Erich Kyle Dodson⁶, and Rachel E. Simons⁷

¹ shayla.williams@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 104 Airport Road, Grangeville, ID 83530, USA

² james.steed@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 5775 W. Broadway Street, Missoula, MT 59808, USA

³ jeremy.morrone@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 337 Antelope Trail, Whitefish, MT 59937, USA

⁴ sara.goeking@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Research and Development, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 860 N 1200 E, Logan, UT 84321, USA

⁵ mlavin@montana.edu; Montana State University, 119 Plant Bioscience Bldg, Bozeman 59717-3150, USA

⁶ erich.k.dodson@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 4919 S 1500 W, Ste 200, Riverdale, UT 84405, USA

⁷ rachel.simons@usda.gov; USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Forest Inventory and Analysis, 5775 W. Broadway Street, Missoula, MT 59808, USA

Acknowledgements: We would like to thank all RMRS-FIA field crews for collecting the data and samples that made this work possible. We also thank Montana State University Plant Sciences Department for providing lab supplies used for genetic analysis. We extend sincere gratitude to the editors and anonymous reviewers, whose comments led to substantial improvements of this paper. This work was supported in part by the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Inventory & Analysis Program at Rocky Mountain Research Station. The findings and conclusions in this publication are those of the authors and should not be construed to represent any official USDA or U.S. Government determination or policy. This article was prepared in part by employees of the USDA Forest Service as part of official duties and is therefore in the public domain in the U.S.

ABSTRACT:

1 Accurate identification of whitebark and limber pine has become increasingly important
2 following the 2022 listing of whitebark pine as a threatened species under the Endangered Species Act.
3 However, morphological similarities make identification of the two species difficult where ranges
4 overlap. Using a genetic test that differentiates whitebark and limber pine, we compared field
5 identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis field crews with genetic identification for needle samples
6 from 371 trees. Field identifications were 100% correct for the 76 samples collected from outside regions
7 of species' range overlap. Eighty-three percent of the field identifications were correct in regions of
8 range overlap (89% for large trees, 88% for saplings, and 78% for seedlings). Field-identified samples
9 were correct 60% of the time for limber pine and >99% for whitebark pine. Random forests analysis
10 revealed that identification accuracy is influenced by crew experience, large (≥ 12.7 cm diameter) limber
11 or whitebark pines recorded by field crews on the plot, elevation, Julian day of sample collection, and
12 habitat type. We found that whitebark pine has likely been underestimated, and limber pine
13 overestimated, within their overlapping ranges. We provide insights on improving accuracy of future
14 monitoring where these species overlap.

15 **KEYWORDS:** Forest inventory; genetic identification; whitebark pine; limber pine; quality assessment

STUDY IMPLICATIONS:

1 Accurate identification of whitebark pine is critical for monitoring this threatened
2 species, yet distinguishing whitebark from limber pine can be difficult. Genetic analysis
3 determined accuracy of field identification by Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) crews was 83%
4 where the species' ranges overlap. Virtually all individuals identified as whitebark pine were
5 genetically confirmed to be whitebark pine, although nearly 40% of individuals identified as
6 limber pine were actually whitebark pine. Thus, previous data underestimated whitebark and
7 overestimated limber pine abundance in the species' range overlap. These results quantify
8 reliability of FIA data for whitebark pine assessments and identify areas for improvement.

1 **INTRODUCTION:**

2 High-elevation five-needle pines, which include whitebark pine (*Pinus albicaulis* Engelm.) and
3 limber pine (*Pinus flexilis* James), play important roles in high-mountain ecosystems across western
4 North America. These species provide a host of ecological and cultural benefits including serving as
5 keystone or foundational species (Tomback et al. 2011), providing wildlife food and habitat, creating and
6 sustaining biodiversity, facilitating succession, regulating snowpack melt and runoff, reducing soil
7 erosion, and contributing to aesthetic and spiritual values (Steele 1990; Tomback et al. 2001; Tomback
8 and Achuff 2010; Tomback et al. 2011; Windmuller-Campione and Long 2016).

9 Declines in whitebark and limber pine have been observed throughout most of their ranges over
10 the past several decades (Tomback et al. 2001; Tomback et al. 2011; Goeking and Izlar 2018; Goeking and
11 Windmuller-Campione 2021; Burns et al. 2023), with higher mortality rates in recent years (Goeking and
12 Windmuller-Campione 2021; Burns et al. 2023). White pine blister rust (caused by *Cronartium ribicola*
13 Fisch.), mountain pine beetles (*Dendroctonus ponderosae* Hopkins), altered fire regimes, forest
14 succession, climate change, and interactions among these factors have caused declines in both species
15 (Gibson et al. 2008; Tomback and Achuff 2010; Campbell et al. 2011; Tomback et al. 2011; Cleaver et al.
16 2015; Keane et al. 2022; Burns et al. 2023). Because of these ongoing threats, whitebark pine was listed
17 as threatened under the Endangered Species Act by the US Fish and Wildlife Service in December 2022
18 (US Fish and Wildlife Service 2022). Goeking and Windmuller-Campione (2021) noted that limber pine
19 population trends are comparable to the trends exhibited by whitebark pine less than 10 years earlier.

20 Reliable inventory data are required for scientific studies and for monitoring the status of these
21 species (Keane et al. 2022; Tomback and Sprague 2022). However, the similarity between whitebark and
22 limber pines' needles, bark, and growth form make it very difficult to distinguish the two species based
23 on vegetative characteristics alone (Arno and Hammerly 2007; Alongi et al. 2019; Hansen et al. 2021).
24 When present, pollen and seed cones of whitebark and limber pine are sufficiently distinct in color,

25 morphology, and persistence that the two species can be reliably distinguished (Arno and Hoff 1989;
26 McCaughey and Schmidt 2001; Lesica 2012). However, cone-bearing trees of both species are absent
27 from many sites due to widespread mortality (Tomback and Achuff 2010; Keane et al. 2022), branch
28 dieback (i.e., branch death) caused by white pine blister rust (McKinney and Tomback 2007; Tomback
29 and Achuff 2010; Cleaver et al. 2015), seed predation, and unsuitable weather conditions (Hansen et al.
30 2021). Additionally, these slow-growing species can take 20-40 years to produce cones, and large cone
31 crops do not typically occur in whitebark pine until trees are at least 60 to 80 years old (Krugman and
32 Jenkinson 1974; Arno and Hammerly 2007). Thus, cones are often absent from younger trees.

33 The challenge of identifying young trees is exacerbated in disturbed areas, where both species
34 may be pioneering, and in other forest types without five-needle pines in the overstory. In both
35 circumstances, long-distance seed dispersal by Clark's nutcrackers (*Nucifraga columbiana* Wilson) may
36 lead to whitebark pine or limber pine regeneration in these community types if conditions are suitable
37 (Tomback and Linhart 1990; Lorenz et al. 2011; Tomback et al. 2011). Nutcrackers typically disperse seeds
38 up to a few kilometers, routinely transport seeds 12 to 22 km (Tomback and Linhart 1990), and may
39 disperse seeds as far as 32 km (Lorenz et al. 2011), often over large elevation gradients (Tomback and
40 Linhart 1990; Lorenz et al. 2011; Tomback et al. 2011). This dispersion results in regeneration of
41 whitebark and limber pines on sites that may not have trees of these same species in the overstory
42 (Windmuller-Campione and Long 2016; Goeking and Izlar 2018; Goeking et al. 2019; Goeking and
43 Windmuller-Campione 2021). Climate and substrate are also unreliable indicators for species
44 identification, as their effects on species occurrence vary geographically (Arno and Weaver 1990;
45 Hansen-Bristow et al. 1990; McCaughey and Schmidt 2001; Weaver 2001). Additionally, co-occurrence
46 and elevational overlap between whitebark and limber pines has been documented in many areas (Arno
47 and Hoff 1989; Weaver 2001; Resler and Tomback 2008; Hansen et al. 2021).

48 The need to better understand these declining and important species has led to several
49 approaches for addressing identification challenges. For example, some regional monitoring protocols
50 require crews to establish plots in alternate locations if whitebark and limber pine cannot be
51 distinguished in the field at the initial plot location (Greater Yellowstone Whitebark Pine Monitoring
52 Working Group 2011). Whitebark and limber pines are lumped as ‘high-elevation five-needle pines’ in
53 results from USDA Forest Service, Forest Health Protection aerial surveys (Hayes 2016). Tomback et al.
54 (2005) required field crews to be familiar with cone-based species identification in geographic areas with
55 both species, and Resler and Tomback (2008) used needle morphology to distinguish the two species,
56 which requires specialized equipment and knowledge. These methods ensure certain levels of data
57 quality, meet study objectives, and use available resources for identification. However, these approaches
58 are not realistic or reliably effective for field campaigns using probability-based species-specific sampling
59 for all tree ages and species, and new resources (i.e. the genetic testing method detailed in Alongi et al.
60 2019) have recently become available.

61 USDA Forest Service Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) conducts a probability-based, statistically
62 representative sample of whitebark and limber pine occurrence that is frequently used for modeling
63 species distribution and responses to climate change (e.g., Bell et al. 2014; Schoettle et al. 2022; Warwell
64 et al. 2006; Windmuller-Campione and Long 2016). FIA data constitute the primary data source
65 throughout whitebark pine’s range in the US and were cited in the decision to list whitebark pine as
66 threatened (US Fish and Wildlife Service 2022). FIA data continue to be used by the US Forest Service to
67 assess impacts of management on whitebark pine and by researchers who are developing future range
68 projections that will guide restoration efforts. This ongoing reliance on FIA data for whitebark pine
69 assessments assumes that species identification is accurate. Although FIA conducts expert checks for
70 quality control (Gray et al. 2012), in situ quality control is hampered when species cannot be conclusively
71 identified in the field. To improve quality control, we analyzed an existing sample of whitebark and

72 limber pine needles collected from FIA plots using an economical genetic test that differentiates the two
73 species (Alongi et al. 2019).

74 The objectives of this study were to: (1) assess identification accuracy for whitebark pine and
75 limber pine by Rocky Mountain Research Station (RMRS)-FIA field crews; (2) identify factors that predict
76 when misidentification is most likely to occur; and (3) describe steps that can improve future FIA
77 identification of these two species. We hypothesized that difficulty in distinguishing whitebark and
78 limber pine when cones are absent would lead to misidentification, and we predicted that these errors
79 would be more common for seedlings. By examining patterns in misidentification, we identified
80 additional causes of identification errors and provide recommended procedures to improve future data
81 quality.

82 **MATERIALS AND METHODS:**

83 **Study Area**

84 Our study area encompassed regions of whitebark and limber pine range overlap within the
85 states of Montana, Idaho, Wyoming, and Nevada. To define these regions, we first created
86 comprehensive range maps for each species. Maps were built by joining location data from FIA plots
87 containing whitebark and limber pine (as described in Burrill et al. 2023) with digitized range
88 maps developed by the Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation (2014 and 2019) and USDA Forest Service,
89 Forest Health Protection (Forest Health Technology Enterprise Team 2023). We applied a 35 km buffer
90 around each comprehensive range map to encompass the maximum seed dispersal distance of Clark's
91 nutcrackers (Lorenz et al. 2011). Using the intersect tool in ArcGIS, we isolated the area where the
92 buffered ranges overlap. Lastly, we eliminated any areas that fell outside the footprint of RMRS-FIA
93 (Figure 1). The resulting area excluded range overlap in central and southern Sierra Nevada in California,
94 the Wallowa Mountains of northeastern Oregon, and a band that runs through southeastern British
95 Columbia and southwestern Alberta to about 54° north (Tomback et al. 2011). The area of species' range

96 overlap, hereafter referred to as the study area, covered approximately 75% of whitebark pine range
97 within the RMRS-FIA data collection states and included 89% of RMRS-FIA plots with whitebark pine
98 trees (> 12.7 cm diameter). Fifty percent of limber pine range within the RMRS-FIA data collection states
99 and 50% of RMRS-FIA plots with limber pine trees (> 12.7 cm diameter) were in the study area.

100 **Data collection on FIA plots**

101 The FIA plot grid consists of approximately one plot per 2,428 ha, comprising a probability-
102 based, statistically representative sample across all land cover types, forest types, and ownership groups
103 (Bechtold and Patterson 2005; Burrill et al. 2023). Each year, 10% of FIA plots within the RMRS-FIA
104 footprint are targeted for visit and numerous site, stand, and tree variables are measured (USDA 2010).
105 Each FIA plot consists of four 7.3 m radius subplots, covering 672 m² total. All standing live and dead
106 trees ≥ 12.7 cm diameter (hereafter referred to as ‘large trees’) in the subplot are identified to species
107 and numerous measurements are taken. Nested within each subplot is a 2.1 m radius microplot, wherein
108 field crews measure all saplings (≥ 2.5 cm and < 12.7 cm diameter) and record the number of seedlings
109 per species (*Pinus* spp. seedlings are < 2.5 cm diameter and > 15.2 cm height) (USDA 2010). Diameters
110 are measured at breast height (1.37 m above ground level) for whitebark pine and limber pine (see USDA
111 2010 for more detail).

112 **Needle samples**

113 From 2010 to 2012, RMRS-FIA field crews identified all tree species present on each subplot and
114 collected one tissue sample per species from the subplot. Samples were collected from individuals with
115 the following order of preference: 1) large trees on the subplot or saplings on the microplot; 2) seedlings
116 on the microplot; 3) large trees immediately adjacent to the subplot or saplings and seedlings located off
117 the microplot but on the subplot; 4) saplings or seedlings immediately adjacent to the subplot. This
118 method resulted in at least one sample for each field-identified species found on each plot, with a
119 maximum of four samples for each species per plot. Each five-needle pine sample consisted of at least

120 one fascicle of five needles. Samples were placed in envelopes with a small amount of silica gel cat litter
121 and stored in cardboard boxes at the RMRS-FIA lab in Ogden, UT until 2020. Although all species were
122 sampled, this study opportunistically used samples from field-identified whitebark and limber pines.

123 A total of 371 samples from 205 plots had conclusive genetic test results. Of these, 295 samples
124 were collected from 165 plots located within our study area (Figure 1). These 295 samples represent
125 about 2% of the live whitebark and limber pine trees, saplings, and seedlings measured on FIA plots
126 located within the study area. The field identifications of the remaining 76 samples collected outside of
127 the study area were verified as 100% accurate using the genetic identification tool described below and
128 were therefore excluded from our analyses of identifications errors.

129 **Accuracy of species identification**

130 To test species identification by field crews, genetic analyses were conducted in 2020 and 2021
131 by the Plant Sciences and Plant Pathology Department lab at Montana State University using the genetic
132 identification tool detailed in Alongi et al. (2019). This tool uses two chloroplast loci to expeditiously
133 distinguish needle samples of whitebark and limber pine trees. This approach is justifiable, as opposed to
134 a genomic approach, for several reasons. The first is that introgressive hybridization between these two
135 species is not known to occur. Ericson (1965), Bingham (1973), and Critchfield (1986) report cursory to
136 uncertain evidence for whitebark and limber pine putative hybrids, either from single trees or small
137 population samples, and these include results from artificial crosses. These studies provide no evidence
138 of introgressive hybridization between whitebark and limber pine. Second, evidence of introgression
139 between species typically involves delimitation of a hybrid zone that lies in the region of contact
140 between the geographical distributions of two putative parental species, as exemplified by limber pine
141 and southwestern white pine (*Pinus strobiformis* Engelm.; Menon et al. 2018) and whitebark pine and
142 sugar pine (*Pinus lambertiana* Douglas; Liston et al. 2007). No such hybrid zone has been detected in the
143 region of overlap for whitebark and limber pine (e.g., as mapped by Little 1971; Ulrich 2023). Within this

144 region of overlap, Alongi et al. (2019) and follow-up analyses found complete congruence between
145 limber and whitebark pine trees identified using seed-cones and chloroplast haplotypes and these
146 comparisons mostly involved blind tests. Thirdly, our approach would be excessively encumbered by a
147 genomic approach to distinguishing whitebark and limber pine. Genomic analyses have been performed
148 on limber pine (Liu et al. 2016a) and whitebark pine (Liu et al. 2016b; Syring et al. 2016). However, both
149 limber and whitebark pine have large genomes (30.5 Gbp (Liu et al. 2016a) and ~27 Gbp (Syring et al.
150 2016)) that could not be affordably analyzed at a population level (Syring et al. 2016).

151 We determined the species identification accuracy for each sample by comparing the field
152 identification written on the sample envelope (referred to as 'field-identified') to the genetic
153 identification (referred to as 'lab-identified'). Accuracy was then calculated as the percentage of samples
154 that were correctly identified. Of the 295 study area samples, 181 were sampled from large trees,
155 saplings, or seedlings that were measured as a standard part of plot data collection (categorized as 'tally'
156 samples), and 114 were sampled from large trees located off the subplot or saplings or seedlings located
157 off the microplot ('non-tally').

158 To further understand patterns in misidentification, we created a confusion matrix containing
159 data from all samples, and for each size class (seedlings, saplings, large trees, and unknown size).
160 Confusion matrices display 'actual' versus 'predicted' values for two or more classes (in this study lab-
161 identified vs. field-identified) and identify errors of commission and omission. For each confusion matrix,
162 we calculated false positive error rates, sensitivity, and specificity (James et al. 2013) for both whitebark
163 and limber pine:

$$164 \quad \text{False positive error rate} = \frac{n_{\text{false positives}}}{n_{\text{false positives}} + n_{\text{true positives}}}$$

$$165 \quad \text{Sensitivity} = \frac{n_{\text{true positives}}}{n_{\text{true positives}} + n_{\text{false negatives}}}$$

166
$$\textit{Specificity} = \frac{n_{\textit{true negatives}}}{n_{\textit{true negatives}} + n_{\textit{false positives}}}$$

167 False positive error rates identify errors of commission (Type 1 error), e.g., the proportion of limber pine
168 trees that are incorrectly field-identified as whitebark pine. In our study, sensitivity for a species indicates
169 the ability of FIA field crews to correctly field-identify a sample that is lab-identified as that species.
170 Specificity for a given species indicates the field crews' ability to correctly field-identify a sample that is
171 not the given species (i.e., it is lab-identified as the other species). Because our study examined only two
172 species, the specificity of one species was equal to the sensitivity of the other.

173 **Predictors of identification accuracy**

174 To identify predictors of misidentification errors, we developed a list of 12 potential predictors
175 based on guidance given to RMRS-FIA field crews and on a literature review (Table 1). These predictors
176 were grouped into three types of variables: 1) observer-related variables; 2) tree-level variables
177 associated with the presence of cones; and 3) site-level variables that influence species distribution
178 patterns or the likelihood of encountering both species (Table 1).

179 Crew leader experience was calculated as the number of plots with whitebark or limber pine in
180 the study area that a crew leader had measured at the time of sample collection. We aggregated habitat
181 type, which describes the potential (late seral or climax) natural vegetation based on climate, geography,
182 or other site characteristics (Pfister et al. 1977), to the series level (Burrill et al. 2023) resulting in five
183 habitat type series. We aggregated field-recorded forest type (i.e., FLDTYPCD in Burrill et al. 2023), which
184 indicates the predominant live tree species or group of species in the stand (USDA 2010), to six forest-
185 type groups (Burrill et al. 2023). Whitebark pine seed zones defined by Mahalovich and Hipkins (2011)
186 encompass areas of similar environmental conditions and allowed comparison of accuracy rates among
187 areas differing in geology, topography, climate, and vegetation. The 13 samples collected outside of
188 mapped seed zones were placed into the category of 'outside'. We aggregated lithology types from the

189 State Geological Map Compilation database (Horton et al. 2017) to five groups. We determined whether
190 a sample was collected east or west of the Continental Divide by using spatial analyses on a geodatabase
191 feature class of sample locations and a shapefile of the Continental Divide (U.S. Geological Survey 2002).
192 We initially performed analyses using actual elevation and using equivalent elevation, which accounts for
193 the latitudinal range of our study area (Windmuller-Campione and Long 2016), but we report only results
194 based on actual elevation due to lack of significant differences between the two metrics.

195 To identify important predictors of identification accuracy, we developed a random forests model
196 in R package randomForests (R Core Team 2016) using a classification threshold of 0.5 (James et al.
197 2013), with 500 trees for evaluation (parameter ntree = 500 and mtry = 3). We used 10-fold cross-
198 validation to evaluate model performance. We chose random forests because it provides intuitive
199 interpretation of variable importance, is robust to collinearity and interaction among predictor variables,
200 and makes no a priori assumptions about the distributions of response or predictor variables (Cutler et
201 al. 2007). Significant predictors were identified by their corresponding decrease in random forests model
202 accuracy (i.e., not identification accuracy) and Gini index (Cutler et al. 2007; James et al. 2013). Mean
203 decrease in accuracy measures the contribution of each variable to the overall accuracy of the model,
204 whereas Gini index is a measure of node purity (i.e., how accurate is each decision point, or node) within
205 the classification tree (James et al. 2013). The Gini index method of calculating variable importance
206 results in a strong preference for continuous variables or those with many categories (Strobl et al. 2007).

207 To complement modelling, we examined the relationship between predictor variables and
208 identification accuracy. We compared field- versus lab-identified whitebark pine presence across
209 different predictor variable values or categories to better understand the circumstances in which
210 misidentification is most likely to occur. Wilcoxon rank sum tests (for continuous predictor variables) and
211 chi-square tests of association (for categorical predictor variables) were performed to test for significant
212 associations between identification accuracy and the predictor variables (Zar 1996) (critical p-value =

213 0.05 for each method). We calculated Cramer's V scores to determine the strength of association with
214 each categorical predictor variable. Cramer's V scores quantify the strength of the association among
215 two categorical variables, which in our analysis were done via chi-square tests, where the values of V
216 range from zero (no association) to one (perfect association) (Cohen 1988). Values less than or equal to
217 0.3 indicate a weak association, those between 0.4 and 0.5 a medium association, and those greater
218 than 0.5 a strong association. To better understand effects of crew experience, we compared cumulative
219 accuracy for the field crew leader collecting a given sample to that crew leader's experience as of that
220 date. Cumulative accuracy was calculated as mean accuracy of all samples across all plots that a crew
221 leader had collected up to and including each sampling date.

222 **RESULTS:**

223 **Field identification accuracy**

224 Genetic analyses of the 295 needle samples collected within the study area revealed that 218
225 samples came from whitebark pines, and 77 samples came from limber pines. Overall, field identification
226 accuracy was 83% (Table S1 provides details for each misidentified sample). Greater than 99% of samples
227 identified as whitebark pine by field crews were genetically confirmed as whitebark pine. The primary
228 source of error was misidentification of whitebark pines as limber pines, indicated by the 40% false
229 positive rate for limber pine (Table 2), which meant that field crews detected 77% of sampled trees
230 genetically verified as whitebark pines. In contrast, only a single limber pine was misidentified as a
231 whitebark pine. Although identification accuracy was similar for large trees (89%) and saplings (88%), it
232 was notably lower for seedlings (78%). More than half of seedlings identified as limber pine by field
233 crews were whitebark pine, and only 73% of whitebark pine seedlings were correctly identified (Table 2).

234 **Predictors of identification accuracy**

235 Our random forests model correctly classified 88% of observations, based on the predictors in
236 Table 1, and had a Cohen's Kappa value of 0.53 which is generally considered to indicate 'moderate'

237 agreement between actual and predicted values (Cohen 1988). The two indices used to evaluate relative
238 variable importance (mean decrease in accuracy and Gini index) produced different results. Both metrics
239 indicated that crew leader experience had the most impact on identification accuracy. However, large
240 limber pine trees recorded by field crews on the plot and large whitebark pine trees recorded by field
241 crews on the plot had the second and third largest variable importance scores based on mean decrease
242 in accuracy. Elevation and Julian day had the second and third largest variable importance scores based
243 on the mean decrease in Gini index (Figure 2a). The method of calculating variable importance for Gini
244 index likely contributed to the increased relative importance of the three continuous variables (see
245 'Methods' for details).

246 The results of chi-square tests of association (Table 3) and Wilcoxon Rank Sum tests detected
247 significant relationships between identification accuracy and several variables also identified as
248 important by the random forests model (see Table 1 for predictor variable descriptions). For categorical
249 variables, significant associations with identification accuracy were detected for large whitebark pine
250 trees recorded by field crews on the plot, large limber pine trees recorded by field crews on the plot,
251 lithology type, seed zone, forest type group, and size class. Cramer's V scores were highest for large
252 whitebark pines recorded by field crews on the plot (0.346) and large limber pines recorded by field
253 crews on the plot (0.262), suggesting moderate and weak associations, respectively, with identification
254 accuracy. Despite its moderate importance in the random forests model, habitat type was not
255 significantly associated with identification accuracy according to the chi-square test of association.
256 Among our continuous predictors, Wilcoxon Rank Sum tests indicated that only crew leader experience
257 had a significant effect on identification accuracy ($p < 0.001$).

258 **Patterns in misidentification**

259 We quantified the likelihood of misidentification with respect to three types of variables:
260 observer-related, tree-level, and site-level variables. Analysis of observer-related variables indicated that

261 the experience level of the crew leader was an important predictor of identification accuracy. For
262 correctly identified samples, crew leaders had completed an average of 49 whitebark/limber pine plots
263 in the study area, whereas for incorrectly identified samples, crew leaders had completed an average of
264 26 plots ($p < 0.001$, Welch's t-test). Our ability to test whether accuracy increased as individual crew
265 leaders gained experience was limited by low sample sizes from many crew leaders (81% of crew leaders
266 collected samples from less than 10 plots). However, a broad range of experience across all crew leaders
267 revealed a strong correlation ($p < 0.001$, Spearman rank correlation) between crew leader experience
268 and cumulative accuracy, both among crew leaders and even for some individuals as their experience
269 increased (Figure 3). Crew leaders who had measured fewer than 25 plots had highly variable cumulative
270 accuracy (56% correct \pm 50% SD), while more experienced crew leaders were more consistently
271 accurate (91% correct \pm 29% SD). In contrast to crew leader experience, the other observer-related
272 variable, 'tally' versus 'non-tally,' had no significant effect on identification accuracy. This indicates that
273 even though some samples were collected from trees that were not included in the FIA dataset, the
274 accuracy rates and trends were still representative of FIA data.

275 We assessed how cone presence influenced identification accuracy using two tree-level variables
276 associated with the likelihood of cone presence: tree size class and Julian day. To accomplish this, we
277 compared accuracy rates among size classes and tested for relationships between accuracy and Julian
278 day. The clear differences in accuracy among samples collected from seedlings versus from large trees
279 and saplings in our confusion matrices (Table 2) were not supported by the low relative importance of
280 'Size_Class' in the random forests model (Figure 2) and low Cramer's V score (0.176) in the chi-square
281 test (Table 3). This may be due to similar accuracies for large trees and saplings, which likely dampened
282 the effect of seedlings. Julian day, which is an indicator of cone phenology and development, was one of
283 the most important predictors of identification accuracy in the random forests model. A partial
284 dependence plot of Julian day versus identification accuracy revealed that the likelihood of correct

285 identification was relatively low prior to mid-July, reached a peak from mid-August through late-
286 September, and then declined (Figure 2b).

287 The most important site-level predictors of identification accuracy were whether large trees of
288 either species ('PIAL_Trees') or ('PIFL_Trees') were recorded by field crews on the plot, as confirmed by
289 the results of the random forests model (Figure 2), chi-square tests of association (Table 3), and
290 comparison of field-identified versus lab-identified species frequencies (Table 3). We found substantially
291 higher identification accuracy for samples (regardless of tree size) collected from plots where the large
292 trees were recorded as whitebark pine (> 99% accurate), compared to those where they were recorded
293 as limber pine (66% accurate). In addition, all 56 plots where field crews recorded large whitebark pine
294 trees did actually contain lab-identified whitebark pine, while only 32 of 43 plots where field crews
295 recorded large limber pine trees actually contained lab-identified limber pine.

296 We detected associations between identification accuracy and several other site-level variables,
297 although these were weaker than those for field-identified presence of large whitebark and limber pines.
298 Identification accuracy rates varied widely between seed zones, from 91% accuracy in the Inland
299 Northwest (INLA) seed zone to 72% in the Greater Yellowstone – Grand Teton (GYGT) zone (Table 3).
300 Lower identification accuracy within the GYGT seed zone is also associated with sample collection by
301 crew leaders who were less experienced in measuring whitebark and limber pine (Figure 3).

302 Identification accuracy was highest in the whitebark pine and limber pine forest type groups
303 (Table 3). Samples from whitebark pine forest types were dominated by whitebark pine (96% of samples
304 lab-identified as whitebark pine) and contained just one misidentification. Similarly, samples from limber
305 pine forest types were dominated by limber pine (93% of samples lab-identified as limber pine), and also
306 contained just one misidentification. The forest type groups with the highest rates of misidentification
307 were the lodgepole pine and the fir/spruce/mountain hemlock (Table 3).

308 Among habitat type groups, the whitebark pine-timberline and limber pine habitat series had
309 the highest accuracy rates (96% and 88%, respectively), exhibiting a pattern similar to the whitebark pine
310 and limber pine forest type groups. Identification accuracy was lowest (79%) in the subalpine fir series,
311 with a large discrepancy between percent of samples that were lab-identified (98%) versus field-
312 identified (77%) whitebark pine. We detected a strong positive association between whitebark pine
313 occurrence and the presence of subalpine fir (*Abies lasiocarpa* (Hook.) Nutt.); whitebark pine was
314 associated with both the subalpine fir habitat type series (98% of samples lab-identified whitebark pine)
315 and the whitebark pine-timberline series (96% of samples lab-identified whitebark pine), which includes
316 several habitat types that typically contain a subalpine fir component (Pfister et al. 1977). This
317 association is congruous with our finding of high whitebark pine occurrence in the fir/spruce/mountain
318 hemlock forest type; all sites with fir/spruce/mountain hemlock forest types had either subalpine fir or
319 whitebark pine-timberline habitat types.

320 Misidentifications were concentrated where elevational overlap was greatest between the
321 species: 63% of misidentifications were detected between 2,100 m and 2,500 m, despite only 41% of
322 samples coming from this elevation range (Figure 4). The concentration of misidentifications in this range
323 resulted in a significantly higher mean elevation for field-identified limber pine samples (2,134 m) than
324 that of lab-identified limber pine samples (1,973 m) ($p = 0.013$, Welch's t-test). The field-identified
325 elevation range of whitebark pine was not significantly different than the lab-identified range ($p = 0.49$,
326 Welch's t-test), but the shift in limber pine elevation suggests there is more elevational distinction
327 between the species than was reflected in previously collected FIA data. We also observed that
328 misidentification was most prevalent on plots just below 2,500 m (~8,200 ft) (Figure 4 and Figure 2d
329 partial dependence plot), although only 7 samples were lab-identified as limber pine above 2,500 m.

330 We detected a weak association (Cramer's $V = 0.210$) between identification accuracy and
331 lithology type (Table 3). We found that identification was 100% accurate within the carbonate

332 sedimentary lithology type and 44% of samples were lab-identified whitebark pine. However, analysis of
333 identification accuracy among lithology types proved problematic due to the coarse scale of the lithology
334 data (1:1,000,000).

335 We also found that co-occurrence of whitebark and limber pines on the same plot was more
336 common than was recorded by field crews; Of the 79 plots that had more than one sample collected,
337 eight plots had both whitebark and limber pine genetically identified (~10%), whereas field crews did not
338 correctly identify that there were two species present on any plots. Because field crews did not detect
339 more than one species per plot, identification errors occurred on all eight plots where co-occurrence was
340 lab-identified.

341 **DISCUSSION:**

342 We found that trees identified as whitebark pine in the field were correctly identified more
343 frequently than trees that were field-identified as limber pine. This strong error directionality may be
344 due, in part, to the rapid deconstruction of whitebark pine seed cones for seed removal by dispersers
345 (McCaughey and Schmidt 1990). Whitebark pine seed cones mature between mid-August and mid-
346 September, after which they rapidly disintegrate as the seeds are harvested by Clark's nutcrackers and
347 other agents, leaving small remnants or no evidence of cones (Arno and Hoff 1989; McCaughey and
348 Tomback 2001). In contrast, limber pine seed cones often remain present and intact (Tomback et al.
349 2011). When the two species co-occur, crews are more likely to see evidence of limber pine and may be
350 more likely to assign that identification to all high-elevation five needle pines in the area. Additionally,
351 post-predation cone remnants on whitebark pine can be mistaken for persistent limber pine cones and
352 lead to misidentification, even in stands that contain only whitebark pine. In addition to contributing to
353 error directionality, cone phenology provides a potential explanation for the relationship of Julian day
354 and identification accuracy (Figure 2b); higher identification accuracy coincides with the time when
355 mature pollen and seed cones are most likely to be present for whitebark pine. An alternative

356 explanation of the Julian day relationship to identification accuracy is that field crews typically sample
357 their highest elevation plots in August and September, and these plots are more likely to be dominated
358 by whitebark pine (Figure 4); 80% of samples collected from mid-July to late-September were lab-
359 identified whitebark pine, versus 55% and 57% before and after this period, respectively.

360 Our results support our expectation that identification errors would be more prevalent for
361 seedlings compared to saplings and large trees due to the difficulty in distinguishing species if cones are
362 absent. However, differences between the genetic sampling protocol and FIA plot measurements
363 indicate that FIA seedling data may be more accurate than our study suggests, even in the study area
364 (see 'Implications for users of FIA data'). Further, the higher identification accuracy for samples from all
365 size classes in the presence of correctly identified large whitebark pine trees suggests that 1) there is a
366 tendency of crews to assign any five-needle pine regeneration to the same species they recorded in the
367 overstory and 2) higher identification accuracy rates for regeneration on plots with large whitebark pines
368 recorded can be explained by higher identification accuracy rates for large whitebark pines (Table 2).

369 A related finding is that identification accuracy is lower in forest types other than whitebark pine
370 or limber pine types. Two previous studies based on FIA data (Goeking and Izlar 2018; Goeking et al.
371 2019) documented the prevalence of whitebark pine within the fir/spruce/mountain hemlock and
372 lodgepole pine forest type groups and noted particularly high densities of regeneration in stands
373 dominated by lodgepole pine. Our results validate that seedlings identified as whitebark pine were
374 virtually always correct, yet more than half of seedlings identified as limber pine were actually whitebark
375 pine. Thus, although these earlier studies quantified abundant whitebark pine regeneration in multiple
376 forest types, they likely underestimated the prevalence of whitebark pine seedlings.

377 The strong positive association we found between whitebark pine and subalpine fir indicates
378 that, in some regions where the ranges of whitebark and limber pines overlap, the ability of a site to
379 support subalpine fir may serve as a strong predictor of the five-needle pine species present. Pfister et

380 al. (1977) and Steele et al. (1981) found that limber pine occurrence was restricted to just a few of the
381 driest habitat types capable of supporting subalpine fir in Montana and central Idaho, respectively.
382 However, Steele et al. (1983) found that limber pine occurrence was less restricted within habitat types
383 capable of supporting subalpine fir in eastern Idaho and western Wyoming. These resources indicate
384 that, while the whitebark pine – subalpine fir association may be useful for identification in some
385 regions, it may be less reliable in other areas, particularly in the GYGT seed zone, and this relationship
386 warrants more study.

387 Higher error rates in the GYGT seed zone, which is known for challenges in five-needle pine
388 species distinction (Greater Yellowstone Whitebark Pine Monitoring Working Group 2011; Hansen et al.
389 2021), may result from the specific combination of lithologies, habitat types, and forest types found
390 within this seed zone. We found higher representation of some lithology types, habitat type groups, and
391 forest type groups that had lower identification accuracy rates in this seed zone compared to other zones
392 (data not presented). Crew leader experience also had substantial influence on identification accuracy,
393 even though we limited the quantification of crew leader experience to measurements of plots in FIA's
394 annual inventory, and thus potentially excluded experience gained from other field work. We found that
395 crew leaders in the GYGT zone had less experience; thus, experience and seed zone may be confounding
396 factors.

397 Lithology helps determine moisture and nutrient availability and has been tied to whitebark pine
398 and limber pine occurrence patterns (Weaver and Dale 1974; Hansen-Bristow et al. 1990; Weaver 2001).
399 We predicted identification accuracy might be low within the carbonate sedimentary lithology type
400 because resources used by field crews (e.g., Pfister et al. 1977; Steele et al. 1981) mention an affinity for
401 calcareous (i.e., carbonate) substrates by limber pine and not by whitebark pine, yet comprehensive
402 reviews of species substrate preferences suggest this is true only in specific geographic areas (Hansen-
403 Bristow et al. 1990; Weaver 2001). However, this prediction was not supported by our results; all

404 samples collected from sedimentary (carbonate) lithology type were accurately identified. Although we
405 found a weak overall association between identification accuracy and lithology type, the possibility that
406 samples were collected from inclusions of different lithology types in the coarser scale lithology polygons
407 make this association questionable. If site-specific lithology data were available for RMRS-FIA plots, this
408 analysis would be more useful.

409 Though we did not examine co-occurrence as a predictor variable, our results indicate that the
410 potential for identification errors markedly increases on sites where whitebark and limber pines co-
411 occur, as noted by others (Greater Yellowstone Whitebark Pine Monitoring Working Group 2011; Hansen
412 et al. 2021) . Because sample collection was limited to a maximum of four samples of each species per
413 plot, true co-occurrence rates are likely higher than the 10% rate we detected. The likelihood of co-
414 occurrence indicates that definitive identification features (e.g., mature cones) on one tree cannot
415 reliably be used to identify nearby trees. This implication poses additional challenges to field crews
416 tasked with identifying trees of all ages in a fixed area and underscores the importance of providing
417 additional identification tools (i.e. genetic analysis).

418 **Implications for users of FIA data**

419 Genetic analysis of whitebark and limber pine samples revealed misidentification rates that
420 exceed FIA's data quality standards. Although over 99% of samples identified as whitebark pine by field
421 crews were actually whitebark pine, the misidentification of many whitebark pine as limber pine meant
422 that field crews correctly identified large trees, saplings, and seedlings of whitebark and limber pine only
423 89%, 88%, and 78% of the time, respectively. FIA objectives are to correctly identify species $\geq 95\%$ of the
424 time for large trees and saplings and $\geq 85\%$ for seedlings (USDA 2010). Although these misidentification
425 rates are based on FIA field crew measurements, they are likely indicative of error rates from other field-
426 based identification of whitebark and limber pines by trained monitoring crews.

427 These samples were analyzed opportunistically, relying on a previous sampling strategy designed
428 to compare genetics of all tree species across broad scales; thus, sampling was not specifically intended
429 to distinguish whitebark and limber pines. Because crews did not know these samples would be used to
430 test identification accuracy, the effort devoted to identification of these samples is likely representative
431 of RMRS-FIA identification. The geographic range of the original sampling protocol provided 76
432 whitebark and limber pine samples collected outside of the study area. Genetic analysis verified that
433 field identification was 100% accurate for both species outside the study area, indicating that the
434 implications of identification errors are confined to the area of range overlap.

435 The differences between genetic sample collection protocols and FIA field methods create some
436 challenges for understanding implications for FIA data. Foliage collection was limited to one sample per
437 subplot for each species identified in the field, for a maximum of four samples per species per plot. The
438 sample limit, paired with the common assumption that only one 5-needle pine species was present on a
439 plot, reduced the likelihood of identifying undetected species co-occurrence, including dispersed
440 seedlings of a 5-needle pine species not present in the overstory. Needle collection protocol for this
441 study only called for sampling from seedlings when larger, potentially cone-bearing trees were absent
442 from the subplot or when needles could not be reached on these trees, whereas RMRS-FIA protocol
443 measures seedling species regardless of large tree presence. Field crews typically assume that whitebark
444 and limber pine seedlings match the species of nearby large trees. Our results corroborate this
445 assumption on plots with large whitebark pine, which account for approximately 65% of plots with
446 whitebark or limber pine in the study area. This suggests that large tree presence likely increases
447 accuracy on the majority of FIA plots. Seventy-one percent of plots that have whitebark seedlings in
448 recently published FIA data (2010-2019) also have large trees on plot, whereas only 60% of plots with
449 seedlings collected in this study had large trees present on plot. This indicates that whitebark and limber
450 pine seedling identification is likely somewhat better throughout FIA data than our results suggest, even

451 within the species' range overlap. However, the 2010-2012 sampling design limits the ability to quantify
452 seedling identification accuracy for these species in the broader sample of FIA data.

453 Despite sampling limitations, this study does help FIA data users understand whether
454 misidentifications introduce substantial bias to estimates of whitebark and limber pine numbers derived
455 from FIA data. Our results suggest that, within our study area, whitebark pine abundance has been
456 underestimated, while limber pine abundance has been overestimated. If we wish to quantify the impact
457 of this bias, we must make several assumptions. First, we must assume that the selected samples are
458 representative of the overall population of whitebark and limber pines on RMRS-FIA plots within our
459 study area. In our study, this is likely true for large trees and saplings, but not for seedlings, suggesting
460 that our results should not be used to quantify the impact of misidentifications on estimations of
461 seedling numbers. Second, we must assume that misidentification rates are similar between the 2010-
462 2012 study period and other years of data collection.

463 The sample design only evaluated live trees; therefore, factors related to misidentification
464 cannot directly inform whether bias in species identification would be substantially different for dead
465 trees. However, some information can be inferred based upon the methods of FIA data collection. For
466 example, dead trees in the FIA dataset are either 1) trees that were dead at the time of initial plot
467 establishment or 2) trees that were alive at a previous plot visit and have since died. Patterns of
468 misidentification are likely similar to those of live trees for the latter because the initial identification was
469 made when the tree was alive. Our results provide no evidence that live and dead whitebark pine trees
470 were underestimated at different rates or that previously published estimates of live-to-dead ratios of
471 whitebark pine trees (Goeking and Izlar 2018) are biased.

472 In addition to affecting estimates of tree numbers, bias resulting from species misidentifications
473 has implications for the use of FIA data in species distribution modelling. Our results indicate that data
474 used to develop species distribution models for whitebark pine on forestland likely include only a few

475 cases where the trees are actually limber pines. However, these models are likely missing additional
476 locations where whitebark pine was present but was misidentified as limber pine. Further, we found that
477 misidentifications were not evenly distributed with respect to elevation and habitat type series, which
478 are closely correlated with climatic conditions (Pfister et al. 1977; Steele et al. 1981). However, because
479 field- and lab-identified elevation ranges of whitebark pine samples were not significantly different,
480 inferences based on FIA data concerning the elevation distribution of whitebark pine should remain
481 valid. Given that we found that 40% of samples field-identified as limber pine were actually whitebark
482 pine, species distribution modeling of limber pine based on FIA data likely contain more errors of
483 commission (i.e., predicting limber pine presence where it does not occur) in areas of range overlap with
484 whitebark pine. Additionally, significantly higher mean elevation for field-identified limber pine samples
485 than that of lab-identified limber pine samples means that inferences based on FIA data about the
486 elevation distribution of limber pine need to be reevaluated. While some of these results provide
487 assurance of data quality, they also indicate that it is important to implement tools that improve
488 identification accuracy, not only within FIA, but also for any probability-based field studies of these two
489 species in regions of range overlap.

490 Our results indicate ways the FIA program, and other studies that rely on field-based species
491 identification, can improve identification accuracy. First, sample protocols should prioritize non-cone-
492 bearing trees for genetic analyses that provide definitively accurate identification of these individuals
493 (Alongi et al. 2019; Hansen et al. 2021). The genetic analyses have proven relatively economical; current
494 laboratory costs are about \$20 per sample (with added costs and time for sample collection, cataloging,
495 and shipping). Needle sampling and lab verification could also be applied beyond the zone of overlap to
496 validate these two species' geographic ranges and potentially identify populations outside their currently
497 known range. However, such an objective would require a larger sample size than used in the current
498 study. Second, trends in crew leader experience suggest that training on whitebark pine versus limber

499 pine identification led by experienced personnel could increase accuracy when cones are absent and
500 genetic analyses is not possible, such as when a tree is dead, needles are out of reach, or cost is
501 prohibitive. Suggested training would include how to use important site-level predictor variables such as
502 forest type and habitat type and would emphasize that species identification should be made at the tree
503 versus stand level, since co-occurrence is more likely than expected.

504 These two approaches for improving quality complement each other; as the data from genetic
505 identification efforts provide a more comprehensive accounting of error and species occurrence
506 patterns, training materials can be improved. Our results indicate that improved training may increase
507 future data quality, even in studies which may not have the means for genetic identification. Based on
508 these results, in 2022 RMRS-FIA implemented a protocol that aims to genetically identify all non-cone
509 bearing large trees, all saplings, and up to 5 seedlings per subplot of whitebark and limber pine.
510 Improved data quality is important not only for FIA and other field-based monitoring programs, but also
511 for improved accuracy of models and maps of seedling niches and climate change projections, all of
512 which rely on field-based observations for calibration and validation.

513 **Conclusions:**

514 Identification accuracy of whitebark and limber pines by RMRS-FIA field crews fell below FIA's
515 data quality standards for all tree size classes in our study area. With respect to whitebark pine, field
516 crew identifications showed high specificity (< 1% of limber pines were field-identified as whitebark
517 pines) but relatively low sensitivity (about 25% of whitebark pines were not field-identified as such). This
518 resulted in underestimation of whitebark pine abundance and overestimation of limber pine abundance.
519 Species distribution modelling efforts calibrated with FIA data will include very few false presences of
520 whitebark pine, although some sites with whitebark pine present will be omitted from calibration
521 datasets. In contrast, species distribution models for limber pine will be influenced by a greater number
522 of false positives that could negatively affect model accuracy.

523 Misidentifications were confined to regions of range overlap, implying that potential biases were
524 limited to those geographic areas. Within regions of range overlap, sampling limitations make it difficult
525 to quantify the true impact of biases on estimates of whitebark and limber pine numbers as well as
526 ratios of dead to live trees. Despite sampling limitations, we found that co-occurrence of whitebark and
527 limber pines was more common than recorded by field crews and that seedling identification was
528 particularly challenging. Better understanding of patterns of misidentification gained through this study
529 has helped us develop a path toward improvement that focuses on needle collection from non-cone
530 bearing trees by crews that are trained to use multiple factors for species identification.

531 **Table titles and figure captions:**

532 **Table 1.** Summary of predictor variables as potential determinants of field identification accuracy.

533 **Table 2.** Species identification accuracy metrics. PIAL = whitebark pine; PIFL = limber pine.

534 **Table 3.** Whitebark and limber pine identification across nine categorical predictor variables. Predictors
535 with significant associations with identification accuracy according to chi-square contingency tests have
536 Cramer's V scores in bold (critical p-value = 0.05). Larger values of Cramer's V indicate stronger
537 association.

538 **Figure 1.** Map of study location and whitebark and limber pine in the Rocky Mountain Research Station-
539 Forest Inventory and Analysis (RMRS-FIA) states*. Symbology for plot locations inside the study area (a)
540 indicates the species present and accuracy of identification(s) (ID) on each plot. Samples from outside
541 the study area were all correctly field-identified in agreement with the species range maps. The buffered
542 ranges of whitebark pine (b) and limber pine (c) are based FIA records of whitebark and limber pine and
543 range maps from Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation (2014 and 2019) and USDA Forest Service,
544 Forest Health Protection (Forest Health Technology Enterprise Team 2023). *RMRS-FIA states: Arizona,
545 Colorado, Idaho, Montana, Nevada, New Mexico, Utah, and Wyoming.

546 **Figure 1 alt text:** Maps of the study area labeled a-c: 1a) A map of Colorado, Idaho, Montana, Nevada,
547 Utah, and Wyoming with the outlined study area, range maps for whitebark and limber pine, and needle
548 sample collection locations. 1b and 1c) Maps of all Rocky Mountain states with points for all FIA plots
549 that had field-identified whitebark pine (1b) and limber pine (1c) and the 35-kilometer buffered range of
550 each respective species.

551 **Figure 2.** Results of random forests classifications used to predict identification accuracy. The variable
552 importance plots (a) present the relative importance of each variable in predicting if a sample was
553 correctly or incorrectly identified. Variables are listed in order of relative importance from top to bottom,
554 with higher mean decrease accuracy and mean decrease Gini values corresponding to greater variable

555 importance. Panels b-f are partial dependence plots providing a graphical depiction of the marginal
556 effect of a given variable on the likelihood of correct identification across different predictor variable
557 values. The y-axis values are similar to a logit scale, with higher values indicating a higher likelihood of
558 correct identification (see Cutler et al. 2007, Appendix C). Variables are described in Table 1.

559 **Figure 2 alt text:** Graphical outputs from random forests modeling, labeled a-f: 2a) A pair of plots
560 showing the relative importance values of nine predictor variables (y-axes) in relation to mean decrease
561 in accuracy (left) and Gini coefficient (right) (x-axes). 2b-f) Plots depicting the marginal effects of the
562 most important predictor variables on the likelihood of correct identification: Julian day (2b), crew leader
563 experience (2c), elevation (2d), field recorded presence or absence of large whitebark pine trees on plot
564 (2e), and field recorded presence or absence of large limber pine trees on plot (2f).

565 **Figure 3.** Crew leader experience and cumulative accuracy across seed zones. Cumulative accuracy
566 increases and becomes less variable for crew leaders with more experience (a). Crew leaders typically
567 work within a specific geographic area; the distribution of experience across seed zones of sample
568 collection (b) illustrates how geographic location and associated variables interact with trends in crew
569 leader accuracy.

570 **Figure 3 alt text:** Graphs of crew leader experience labeled a-b: 3a) A scatter plot with a trendline that
571 shows cumulative accuracy (y-axis) related to crew lead experience (x-axis). The color and symbol of each
572 point represents the seed zone and crew leader identity, respectively, of each sample collection. 3b) Box
573 plots show the distribution of crew leader experience in each seed zone.

574 **Figure 4.** Elevational distribution of whitebark and limber pine needle samples (n = 295). Stacked bars
575 show the elevational distribution of correct and incorrectly identified samples for each species (a). Lab-
576 identified limber pine (*Pinus flexilis*) is displayed in green, and lab-identified whitebark pine (*Pinus*
577 *albicaulis*) is displayed in purple. Darker shading of each color indicates samples that were correctly field-
578 identified, and lighter shading indicates incorrect field-identification. The effects of identification error

579 on elevation distribution are illustrated by a comparison of box plots of elevation range based on lab-
580 identified versus field-identified whitebark pine (b) and limber pine (c).

581 **Figure 4 alt text:** Graphs of field- and lab-identified elevation, labeled a-c: 4a) Stacked bars show the
582 number of samples collected (y-axis) across elevation range (x-axis). 4b and 4c) Box plots show the
583 elevation distribution of samples lab-identified and field-identified as whitebark pine (4b) and limber
584 pine (4c).

585 **Literature Cited:**

- 586 Alongi, Franklin, Andrew J. Hansen, David Laufenberg, Robert E. Keane, Kristin Legg, and Matt Lavin. "An
587 Economical Approach to Distinguish Genetically Needles of Limber from Whitebark Pine." *Forests* 10, no.
588 12 (2019): 1060. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10121060>.
- 589 Arno, Stephen F., and Ramona P. Hammerly. *Northwest Trees: Identifying and Understanding the Region's*
590 *Native Trees*. Anniversary ed., rev. Ed. Seattle, WA: Mountaineers Books, 2007.
- 591 Arno, Stephen F., and Raymond Hoff. 1989. *Silvics of Whitebark Pine (Pinus albicaulis)*. Gen. Tech. Rep.
592 INT-253. USDA Forest Service, Intermountain Research Station, Ogden, UT. 11p.
- 593 Arno, Stephen F., and T. Weaver. 1990. "Whitebark Pine Community Types and Their Patterns on the
594 Landscape." P. 97-105 in *Proceedings - Symposium on Whitebark Pine Ecosystems: Ecology and*
595 *Management of a High-Mountain Resource*, Wyman C. Schmidt and Kathy J. McDonald (ed.s). Gen. Tech.
596 Rep. INT-270. USDA Forest Service, Intermountain Research Station, Ogden, UT.
- 597 Bechtold, W., and P. Patterson. 2005. "The Enhanced Forest Inventory and Analysis Program – National
598 Sampling Design and Estimation Procedures." Gen. Tech. Rep. SRS-80. USDA Forest Service, Southern
599 Research Station, Asheville, NC. 85 p.
- 600 Bell, David M., John B. Bradford, and William K. Lauenroth. "Early Indicators of Change: Divergent Climate
601 Envelopes between Tree Life Stages Imply Range Shifts in the Western United States: Early Indications of
602 Tree Range Shift." *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 23, no. 22 (2014): 168–80. 414
603 <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12109>.
- 604 Bingham, Richard T. "Taxonomy, crossability, and relative blister rust resistance of 5-needled white
605 pines." P. 271-278 in *Biology of rust resistance in forest trees*, Richard. T. Bingham, Raymond J. Hoff, and
606 GERAL I. McDonald (ed.s), Miscellaneous Publication 1221. Washington, DC: USDA Forest Service, 1973.
- 607 Burns, Kelly S., Wade T. Tinkham, K. A. Leddy, Anna W. Schoettle, William R. Jacobi, and Jane E. Stewart.
608 "Interactions between White Pine Blister Rust, Bark Beetles, and Climate over Time Indicate
609 Vulnerabilities to Limber Pine Health." *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change* 6 (April 2023): 1149456.
610 <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2023.1149456>.
- 611 Burrill, Elizabeth A., Glenn A. Christensen, Barbara L. Conkling, Andrea M. DiTomasso, Lucie Lepine, Carol
612 J. Perry, Scott A. Pugh, Jeffery A. Turner, David Walker, Mary A. Williams. 2023. "The Forest Inventory
613 and Analysis Database: Database Description and User Guide for Phase 2 (Version 9.1)." USDA Forest
614 Service. [https://www.fs.usda.gov/research/understory/forest-inventory-and-analysis-database-user-
615 guide-phase-2](https://www.fs.usda.gov/research/understory/forest-inventory-and-analysis-database-user-guide-phase-2).
- 616 Campbell, Elizabeth M., Robert E. Keane, Evan R. Larson, Michael P. Murray, Anna W. Schoettle, and
617 Carmen Wong. 2011. "Disturbance Ecology of High-Elevation Five-Needle Pine Ecosystems in Western
618 North America." P. 154-163 in *The Future of High-Elevation, Five- Needle White Pines in Western North*
619 *America: Proceedings of the High Five Symposium*, Robert E. Keane, Diana F. Tomback, Michael P Murray,
620 and Cyndi M. Smith (ed.s), Proceedings RMRS-P-63. USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research
621 Station, Fort Collins, CO.

622 Cleaver, Christy M., William R. Jacobi, Kelly S. Burns, and Robert E. Means. "Limber Pine in the Central
623 and Southern Rocky Mountains: Stand Conditions and Interactions with Blister Rust, Mistletoe, and Bark
624 Beetles." *Forest Ecology and Management* 358 (December 2015): 139–53.
625 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2015.09.010>.

626 Cohen, J. *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. 3rd ed. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum,
627 1988.

628 Critchfield, William B. "Hybridization and classification of the white pines (*Pinus* section *Strobus*)." *Taxon*
629 35 (1986): 647–56.

630 Cutler, D. Richard, Thomas C. Edwards, Karen H. Beard, Adele Cutler, Kyle T. Hess, Jacob Gibson, and
631 Joshua J. Lawler. "Random Forests for Classification in Ecology." *Ecology* 88, no. 11 (2007): 2783–92.
632 <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-0539.1>.

633 Ericson, John E. "A suspected hybrid between *Pinus albicaulis* Engelm. and *Pinus flexilis* James."
634 *Proceedings of the Montana Academy of Sciences* 25 (1965): 58-59.

635 Forest Health Technology Enterprise Team. 2023. "FHP: Basal Area of Whitebark Pine." Raster Dataset.
636 The Individual Tree Species Parameter Maps (ITSP). [https://www.fs.usda.gov/foresthealth/applied-](https://www.fs.usda.gov/foresthealth/applied-sciences/mapping-reporting/indiv-tree-parameter-maps.shtml)
637 [sciences/mapping-reporting/indiv-tree-parameter-maps.shtml](https://www.fs.usda.gov/foresthealth/applied-sciences/mapping-reporting/indiv-tree-parameter-maps.shtml).

638 Gibson, Ken, Kjerstin Skov, Sandy Kegley, Carl Jorgensen, Sheri Smith, and Jeff Witcosky. 2008. *Mountain*
639 *Pine Beetle Impacts in High-Elevation Five-Needle Pines: Current Trends and Challenges*. R1-08–020.
640 USDA Forest Service, Forest Health Protection, Washington, DC. 32 p.

641 Goeking, Sara A., and Deborah Izlar. "*Pinus albicaulis* Engelm. (Whitebark Pine) in Mixed-Species Stands
642 throughout Its US Range: Broad-Scale Indicators of Extent and Recent Decline." *Forests* 9, no.3 (2018):
643 131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f9030131>.

644 Goeking, Sara A, Deborah K Izlar, and Thomas C Edwards. "A Landscape-Level Assessment of Whitebark
645 Pine Regeneration in the Rocky Mountains, USA." *Forest Science* 65, no. 1 (2019): 87–99.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1093/forsci/fxy029>.

647 Goeking, Sara A., and Marcella A. Windmuller-Campione. "Comparative Species Assessments of Five-
648 Needle Pines throughout the Western United States." *Forest Ecology and Management* 496 (September
649 2021): 119438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119438>.

650 Gray, Andrew, Thomas Brandeis, John Shaw, William McWilliams, and Patrick Miles. "Forest Inventory
651 and Analysis Database of the United States of America (FIA)." *Biodiversity & Ecology* 4 (September
652 2012): 225–31. <https://doi.org/10.7809/b-e.00079>.

653 Greater Yellowstone Whitebark Pine Monitoring Working Group. *Interagency Whitebark Pine Monitoring*
654 *Protocol for the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem, Version 1.1*. Bozeman, MT: Greater Yellowstone
655 Coordinating Committee, 2011. <https://irma.nps.gov/DataStore/Reference/Profile/660369>.

656 Hansen, Andrew J., Alyson East, Robert E. Keane, Matt Lavin, Kristin Legg, Zachary Holden, Chris Toney,
657 and Franklin Alongi. "Is Whitebark Pine Less Sensitive to Climate Warming When Climate Tolerances of
658 Juveniles Are Considered?" *Forest Ecology and Management* 493 (August 2021): 119221.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119221>.

660 Hansen-Bristow, Katherine, Clifford Montagne, and Ginger Schmid. 1990. "Geology, Geomorphology, and
661 Soils within Whitebark Pine Ecosystems." P. 62-71 in *Proceedings - Symposium on Whitebark Pine*
662 *Ecosystems: Ecology and Management of a High-Mountain Resource*, Wyman Schmidt and Kathy
663 McDonald (ed.s). Gen. Tech. Rep. INT-270. USDA Forest Service, Intermountain Research Station, Ogden,
664 UT.

665 Hayes, C. 2016. *Montana Forest Insect and Disease Conditions and Program Highlights - 2015*. Forest
666 Health Protection Report R1-16–17. Missoula, MT: USDA Forest Service, Region 1.

667 Horton, John D., Carma A. San Juan, and Douglas B. Stoesser. 2017. *The State Geologic Map Compilation*
668 *(SGMC) Geodatabase of the Conterminous United States*. Data Series. <https://doi.org/10.3133/ds1052>.

669 James, G., D. Witten, T. Hastie, and R. Tibshirani. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*. New York, NY,
670 USA: Springer, 2013.

671 Keane, Robert E., Anna W. Schoettle, and Diana F. Tomback. "Effective Actions for Managing Resilient
672 High Elevation Five-Needle White Pine Forests in Western North America at Multiple Scales under
673 Changing Climates." *Forest Ecology and Management* 505 (February 2022): 119939.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119939>.

675 Krugman, S.L., and J.L. Jenkinson. "Pinus L. Pine." P. 598-638 in *Seeds of Woody Plants in the United*
676 *States*, C.S. Schopmeyer (ed.). Agriculture Handbook 450. Washington, DC: USDA, Forest Service, 1974.

677 Lesica, Peter. *Manual of Montana Vascular Plants*. Fort Worth, TX: BRIT Press, 2012.

678 Liston, Aaron, Mariah Parker-Defeniks, John V. Syring, Ann Willyard, and Richard Cronn. "Interspecific
679 phylogenetic analysis enhances intraspecific phylogeographic inference: a case study in *Pinus*
680 *lambertiana*." *Molecular Ecology* 16 (2007): 3926–3937.

681 Little, Elbert L. 1971. *Atlas of the United States Trees: Volume 1. Conifers and Important Hardwoods*. 320
682 pages. Miscellaneous Publication 1146. Washington, DC: Department of Agriculture.

683 Liu, Jun-Jun., Anna W. Schoettle, Richard A. Snieszko, et al. "Genetic mapping of *Pinus flexilis* major gene
684 (Cr4) for resistance to white pine blister rust using transcriptome-based SNP genotyping." *BMC Genomics*
685 17 (2016a): 753. DOI 10.1186/s12864-016-3079-2

686 Liu, Jun-Jun, Richard A. Snieszko, Micheal Murray, N. Wang, H. Chen, et al. "Genetic diversity and
687 population structure of whitebark pine (*Pinus albicaulis* Engelm.) in western North America." *PLOS ONE*
688 11, no 12 (2016b) e0167986. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0167986>

689 Lorenz, Teresa J., Kimberly A. Sullivan, Amanda V. Bakian, and Carol A. Aubry. "Cache-Site Selection in
690 Clark's Nutcracker (*Nucifraga columbiana*)." *The Auk* 128, no. 2 (2011): 237–47.
691 <https://doi.org/10.1525/auk.2011.10101>.

692 Mahalovich, Mary F., and Valerie D. Hipkins. 2011. "Molecular Genetic Variation in Whitebark Pine (*Pinus*
693 *albicaulis* Engelm.) in the Inland West." P. 118-32 in *The Future of High-Elevation, Five-Needle White*
694 *Pines in Western North America: Proceedings of the High Five Symposium*, Robert Keane, Diana Tomback,
695 Michael Murray, and Cyndi Smith (ed.s). Proceedings RMRS-P-63. USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain
696 Research Station, Fort Collins, CO. https://www.fs.usda.gov/rm/pubs/rmrs_p063.pdf#page=128.

697 McCaughey, Ward W., and Wyman C. Schmidt. 1990. "Autecology of Whitebark Pine." In Symposium on
698 Whitebark Pine Ecosystems: Ecology and Management of a High-Mountain Resource, edited by Wyman
699 C. Schmidt and Kathy McDonald, 386. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Intermountain
700 Research Station.

701 McCaughey, Ward W., and Wyman Schmidt. "Taxonomy, Distribution, and History." In *Whitebark Pine*
702 *Communities: Ecology and Restoration*, edited by Diana F. Tomback, Stephen F. Arno, and Robert E.
703 Keane, 29-40. Washington, DC: Island Press, 2001.

704 McCaughey, Ward W., and Diana F. Tomback. "The Natural Regeneration Process." In *Whitebark Pine*
705 *Communities: Ecology and Management*, edited by Diana F. Tomback, Stephen F. Arno, and Robert E.
706 Keane, 105–20. Washington, DC: Island Press, 2001.

707 McKinney, Shawn T., and Diana F. Tomback. "The Influence of White Pine Blister Rust on Seed Dispersal in
708 Whitebark Pine." *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 37, no. 6 (2007): 1044–57.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1139/X06-305>.

710 Menon, Mitra, Justin C. Bagley, Christopher J. Friedline, Amy V. Whipple, Anna W. Schoettle, Alejandro
711 Leal-Saenz, Christian Wehenkel, Francisco Molina-Freaner, Lluvia Flores-Renteria, M. Socorro Gonzalez-
712 Elizondo, et al. "The role of hybridization during ecological divergence of southwestern white pine (*Pinus*
713 *strobiformis*) and limber pine (*P. flexilis*)." *Molecular Ecology* 27 (2018): 1245–1260.

714 Pfister, Robert D., Bernard L. Kovalchik, Stephen F. Arno, and Richard C. Presby. 1977. *Forest Habitat*
715 *Types of Montana*. Gen. Tech. Rep. INT-34. USDA Forest Service, Intermountain Forest and Range
716 Experiment Station, Ogden, UT. 174 p.

717 R Core Team. 2016. "R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing." Vienna, Austria. R-
718 project.org.

719 Resler, L. M., & Tomback, D. F. 2008. Blister Rust Prevalence in Krummholz Whitebark Pine: Implications
720 for Treeline Dynamics, Northern Rocky Mountains, Montana, U.S.A. Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine
721 Research, 40(1), 161–170. [https://doi.org/10.1657/1523-0430\(06-116\)JRESLER12.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1657/1523-0430(06-116)JRESLER12.0.CO;2)

722 Schoettle, Anna W., Kelly S. Burns, Shawn T. McKinney, Jodie Krakowski, Kristen M. Waring, Diana F.
723 Tomback, and Marianne Davenport. "Integrating Forest Health Conditions and Species Adaptive
724 Capacities to Infer Future Trajectories of the High Elevation Five-Needle White Pines." *Forest Ecology*
725 *and Management* 521 (October 2022): 120389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2022.120389>.

726 Steele, Robert. "Pinus flexilis James Limber Pine." In *Silvics of North America*, edited by Russell M. Burns
727 and Barbara Honkala, I. Conifers: 348–54. Silvics of North America. USDA Forest Service, 1990.

728 Steele, Robert, Stephen V. Cooper, David M. Ondov, David W. Roberts, and Robert D. Pfister. 1983. *Forest*
729 *Habitat Types of Eastern Idaho-Western Wyoming*. Gen. Tech. Rep. INT-144. USDA Forest Service,
730 Intermountain Forest and Range Experiment Station, Ogden, UT. 122 p. [https://doi.org/10.2737/INT-](https://doi.org/10.2737/INT-GTR-144)
731 [GTR-144](https://doi.org/10.2737/INT-GTR-144).

732 Steele, Robert, Robert D. Pfister, Russell A. Ryker, and Jay A. Kittmans. 1981. *Forest Habitat Types of*
733 *Central Idaho*. Gen. Tech. Rep. INT-114. USDA Forest Service, Intermountain Forest and Range
734 Experiment Station, Ogden, UT. 138 p.

735 Strobl, Carolin, Anne-Laure Boulesteix, Achim Zeileis, and Torsten Hothorn. "Bias in Random Forest
736 Variable Importance Measures: Illustrations, Sources and a Solution." *BMC Bioinformatics* 8, no. 1
737 (2007): 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-8-25>.

738 Syring, John V., Jacob A. Tennessen, Tara N. Jennings, Jill Wegrzyn, Camille Scelfo-Dalbey, and Richard
739 Cronn. "Targeted capture sequencing in whitebark pine reveals range-wide demographic and adaptive
740 patterns despite challenges of a large, repetitive genome." *Frontiers in Plant Science* 7 (2016): 484. doi:
741 10.3389/fpls.2016.00484

742 Tomback, D. F., and P. Achuff. "Blister Rust and Western Forest Biodiversity: Ecology, Values and
743 Outlook for White Pines: Blister Rust and Western Forest Biodiversity." *Forest Pathology* 40, no. 3–4
744 (2010): 186–225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0329.2010.00655.x>.

745 Tomback, Diana F., Peter Achuff, Anna W. Schoettle, John W. Schwandt, and Ron J. Mastrogiuseppe. 2011.
746 "The Magnificent High-Elevation Five-Needle White Pines: Ecological Roles and Future Outlook." P. 2-28
747 in *The Future of High-Elevation Five-Needle White Pines in Western North America: Proceedings of the*
748 *High Five Symposium*, Robert E. Keane, Diana F. Tomback, Michael P. Murray, and Cyndi Smith (ed.s).
749 Proceedings RMRS-P-63. USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Fort Collins, CO.
750 https://www.fs.usda.gov/rm/pubs/rmrs_p063.pdf#page=12.

751 Tomback, Diana F., Stephen F. Arno, and Robert E. Keane. "The Compelling Case for Management
752 Intervention." In *Whitebark Pine Communities: Ecology and Restoration*, edited by Diana F. Tomback,
753 Stephen F. Arno, and Robert E. Keane, 3–25. Washington DC: Island Press, 2001.

754 Tomback, Diana F., Robert E. Keane, Ward W. McCaughey, and Cyndi Smith. "Whitebark Pine Ecosystem
755 Foundation Methods for Surveying and Monitoring Whitebark Pine for Blister Rust Infection and
756 Damage," March 2005.
757 [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265233145_Whitebark_Pine_Ecosystem_Foundation_Metho](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265233145_Whitebark_Pine_Ecosystem_Foundation_Methods_for_Surveying_and_Monitoring_Whitebark_Pine_for_Blister_Rust_Infection_and_Damage)
758 [ds_for_Surveying_and_Monitoring_Whitebark_Pine_for_Blister_Rust_Infection_and_Damage](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265233145_Whitebark_Pine_Ecosystem_Foundation_Methods_for_Surveying_and_Monitoring_Whitebark_Pine_for_Blister_Rust_Infection_and_Damage).

759 Tomback, Diana F., and Yan B. Linhart. "The Evolution of Bird-Dispersed Pines." *Evolutionary Ecology* 4,
760 no. 3 (1990): 185–219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02214330>.

761 Tomback, Diana F., and Eric Sprague. "The National Whitebark Pine Restoration Plan: Restoration Model
762 for the High Elevation Five-Needle White Pines." *Forest Ecology and Management* 521 (October 2022):
763 120204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2022.120204>.

764 Ulrich, Danielle E.M, Chloe Wasteneys, Sean Hoy-Skubik, and Franklin Alongi. "Functional traits underlie
765 specialist-generalist strategies in whitebark pine and limber pine." *Forest Ecology and Management* 542
766 (2023): 121113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121113>

767 US Fish and Wildlife Service. 2022. "Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Threatened Species
768 Status with Section 4 (d) Rule for Whitebark Pine (*Pinus albicaulis*)." Federal Register 87, 76882-76917.

769 US Geological Survey. 2002. "Continental Divide of the United States." Shapefile. National Atlas of the
770 United States. <https://maps.princeton.edu/catalog/stanford-pw312bv3382>.

771 USDA. *Interior West Forest Inventory and Analysis Forest Survey P2 Field Procedures, Ver. 4.0*.
772 Washington, DC: USDA Forest Service, 2010. 370 p.

- 773 Warwell, Marcus V., Gerald E. Rehfeldt, and Nicholas L. Crookston. 2006. Modeling Contemporary
774 Climate Profiles of Whitebark Pine (*Pinus albicaulis*) and Predicting Responses to Global Warming. P. 139-
775 142 In *Proceedings of the Conference Whitebark Pine: A Pacific Coast Perspective*, Ellen M. Goheen and
776 Richard A. Sniezdo (tech. coords.). Portland, OR: USDA Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Region.
- 777 Weaver, T. "Whitebark Pine and Its Environment." P. 41-73 in *Whitebark Pine Communities: Ecology and*
778 *Restoration*, edited by Diana F. Tomback, Stephen F. Arno, and Robert E. Keane. Washington, DC: Island
779 Press, 2001.
- 780 Weaver, T., and D. Dale. "*Pinus albicaulis* in Central Montana: Environment, Vegetation and Production."
781 *American Midland Naturalist* 92, no. 11 (1974): 222. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2424218>.
- 782 Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation. "Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation: Whitebark Pine Range
783 2014." n.d. Scale Range Maximum (zoomed in) 1:500,000 Minimum (zoomed out) 1:150,000,000.
784 https://whitebarkfound.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/WBP_Range_2014_v11.zip.
- 785 Whitebark Pine Ecosystem Foundation. 2019. "Whitebark Pine US Distribution April 2019."
- 786 Windmuller-Campione, Marcella A., and James N. Long. "Limber Pine (*Pinus flexilis* James), a Flexible
787 Generalist of Forest Communities in the Intermountain West." *PLOS ONE* 11, no. 8 (2016): e0160324.
788 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0160324>.
- 789 Zar, J. *Biostatistical Analysis, 3rd Edition*. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1996.

790 **Supplementary materials description:**

791 Table S1: Selected attributes for each sample that was incorrectly identified in the field.

Table 1. Summary of predictor variables as potential determinants of field identification accuracy.

Table 1. Summary of predictor variables as potential determinants of field identification accuracy.

Predictor class	Predictor description	Code	Prediction tested	Source	Type
Observer-related	crew leader experience	Crew_Lead_Experience	ID accuracy is affected by experience in distinguishing five-needle pines	Derived from FIA data ¹	continuous
	'tally' versus 'non-tally' sample	Tally	ID accuracy is affected by whether additional data is collected on the sampled tree	Field sample labels	categorical
Tree-level	size class (large tree, sapling, seedling, unknown)	Size_Class	The presence of reliable ID characteristics such as cones varies by size class	Field sample labels	categorical
	Julian day sample collected	Julian_Day	Phenology and cone development influence ID accuracy	Calculated from FIA data	continuous
Site-level	actual elevation (m)	Elevation_Actual	Species occurrence varies with actual elevation, influencing ID accuracy	FIA data (ELEV)	continuous
	habitat type series	Habitat_Type	Species occurrence varies by habitat type, influencing ID accuracy	FIA data (HABTYPCD1)	categorical
	forest type (field designation)	Forest_Type	Species occurrence varies by forest type, influencing ID accuracy	FIA data (FLDTYPCD)	categorical
	whitebark pine seed zone	Seed_Zone	Species occurrence varies by seed zone, influencing ID accuracy	Mahalovich and Hipkins	categorical
	lithology type	Lithology	ID accuracy is affected by assumptions made about species/substrate relationships	SGMC ²	categorical
	large whitebark pine trees recorded (≥ 12.7 cm diameter)	PIAL_Trees	ID accuracy of immature trees is affected by large PIAL trees recorded on the plot	Derived from FIA data ³	categorical
	large limber pines trees recorded (≥ 12.7 cm diameter)	PIFL_Trees	ID accuracy of immature trees is affected by large PIFL trees recorded on the plot	Derived from FIA data ³	categorical
	East/West of Continental Divide	East_West_CD	Species occurrence varies by location east or west of the divide, influencing ID accuracy	Derived from FIA data	categorical

¹Determined for each sample by counting the number of FIA plots in the study area with whitebark pine and/or limber pine present that a crew leader had measured at the time of sample collection.

²State Geological Map Compilation database

³Determined from data entered by field crews (field-identified) and not from genetic (lab-identified) verifications. As such, these variables suggest whether the field crew believed that large trees of whitebark or limber pine were present on the plot, not whether they were genetically confirmed.

Table 2. Species identification accuracy metrics. PIAL = whitebark pine; PIFL = limber pine.

Tree size class	Number of samples	Proportion correctly identified	PIAL false positive	PIFL false positive	PIAL sensitivity/ PIFL specificity	PIFL sensitivity/ PIAL specificity
All samples	295	0.83	0.01	0.40	0.77	0.99
Seedlings only	103	0.78	0.00	0.56	0.73	1.00
Saplings only	43	0.88	0.00	0.22	0.80	1.00
Large trees only (≥ 12.7 cm dbh)	115	0.89	0.00	0.30	0.85	1.00
Unknown size only	34	0.71	0.06	0.50	0.62	0.90

Table 3. Whitebark and limber pine identification across nine categorical predictor variables.

Table 3. Whitebark and limber pine identification across nine categorical predictor variables. Predictors that are significantly associated with identification accuracy, as determined by chi-square contingency tests, have Cramer's V scores in bold (critical p-value = 0.05). Larger values of Cramer's V indicate stronger association.

Code	Category	Percent of samples identified as whitebark pine		Sample count	Percent of correctly identified samples	Cramer's V of identification accuracy
		FIELD	LAB			
Tally	YES	62	77	181	85	0.070
	NO	49	68	114	79	
Size_Class	Seedling	60	83	103	78	0.176³
	Sapling	47	58	43	88	
	Tree	62	73	115	89	
	Unknown	47	71	34	71	
Habitat_Type ¹	ABLA	77	98	173	79	0.145 ⁴
	PIAL-Timberline	100	96	25	96	
	PIFL	0	10	39	90	
	PSME	12	31	49	82	
	Other	56	67	9	89	
Forest_Type	Douglas-fir Group	33	48	69	86	0.194⁴
	Fir/Spruce/Mountain Hemlock Group	77	97	71	80	
	Limber Pine Group	0	7	15	93	
	Lodgepole Pine Group	71	97	89	74	
	Whitebark Pine Group	100	96	24	96	
	Other forest type groups	15	22	27	93	
Seed_Zone ²	BTIP	74	89	57	84	0.207⁴
	CLMT	54	65	92	89	
	GYGT	50	76	101	72	
	INLA	75	84	32	91	
	Outside	15	23	13	92	
Lithology	Igneous	79	95	82	84	0.210⁴
	Metamorphic	65	83	89	82	
	Sedimentary (carbonate)	44	44	16	100	
	Sedimentary (other)	34	46	83	86	
	Unconsolidated	44	84	25	60	
PIAL_Trees	Present	100	99	118	99	0.346
	Absent	29	57	177	72	
PIFL_Trees	Present	0	34	83	66	0.262
	Absent	80	90	212	89	
East_West_CD	East	48	63	179	84	0.027
	West	72	91	116	81	

¹ABLA = *Abies lasiocarpa* series, PIAL-TIMBERLINE = *Pinus albicaulis* and timberline habitat types, PIFL = *Pinus flexilis* series, PSME = *Pseudotsuga* series, Other = other habitat types

²Whitebark pine seed zones from Mahalovich and Hipkins (2011): BTIP = Bitterroots – Idaho Plateau, CLMT = Central Montana, GYGT = Greater Yellowstone – Grand Teton, INLA = Inland Northwest, Outside = Nevada seed zone or outside any of the seed zones

³Not significant if UNKNOWN category is excluded

⁴25% or more of cells have expected counts < 5.

Figure 1. Map of study location and whitebark and limber pine in the Rocky Mountain Research Station-Forest Inventory and

Figure 2 Results of random forests classifications used to predict identification accuracy

Figure 3 Crew leader experience and cumulative accuracy across seed zones

Figure 4 Elevational distribution of whitebark and limber pine needle samples

Table S1. Selected attributes for each sample that was incorrectly identified in the field.												
Number of samples collected on plot ¹	Size class of sampled tree	Species ² (lab-identified)	Elevation in meters (approx ³)	Julian day of sample collection	Crew leader ⁴	Crew leader experience ⁵	Number of Five-Needle Pines Recorded on the Plot					
							<i>Pinus albicaulis</i>			<i>Pinus flexilis</i>		
							Large trees	Saplings	Seedlings	Large trees	Saplings	Seedlings
<u>2</u>	Sapling	PIAL	2655	265	C	66	0	0	2	1	0	2
1	Sapling	PIAL	2307	180	X	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
<u>2</u>	Sapling	PIAL	2195	251	V	38	0	0	0	2	0	0
<u>3</u>	Sapling	PIAL	2387	221	V	35	0	0	0	3	3	9
1	Sapling	PIAL	2454	224	N	1	0	0	0	0	1	5
4	Seedling	PIAL	2396	181	U	4	0	0	0	0	0	10
4	Seedling	PIAL	2396	181	U	4	0	0	0	0	0	10
4	Seedling	PIAL	2396	181	U	4	0	0	0	0	0	10
4	Seedling	PIAL	2396	181	U	4	0	0	0	0	0	10
1	Seedling	PIAL	1795	264	U	13	0	0	0	0	0	1
1	Seedling	PIAL	2548	185	U	5	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	Seedling	PIAL	2365	221	U	9	0	0	0	0	0	3
1	Seedling	PIAL	2597	215	U	8	0	0	0	2	0	3
2	Seedling	PIAL	2268	222	D	52	0	0	0	1	0	0
1	Seedling	PIAL	2402	223	V	36	0	0	0	0	0	0
<u>3</u>	Seedling	PIAL	2259	272	B	97	0	0	0	3	0	1
<u>4</u>	Seedling	PIAL	2128	278	Z	4	0	0	0	1	1	0
3	Seedling	PIAL	2335	181	I	22	0	0	0	0	0	6
3	Seedling	PIAL	2335	181	I	22	0	0	0	0	0	6
1	Seedling	PIAL	2158	260	E	93	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	Seedling	PIAL	2801	251	Q	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
3	Seedling	PIAL	2786	240	P	25	0	0	0	1	0	5
3	Seedling	PIAL	2786	240	P	25	0	0	0	1	0	5
3	Seedling	PIAL	2786	240	P	25	0	0	0	1	0	5
1	Seedling	PIAL	2536	278	R	12	0	0	0	1	0	1
3	Seedling	PIAL	2914	234	N	3	0	0	0	2	0	8
3	Seedling	PIAL	2914	234	N	3	0	0	0	2	0	8

1	Seedling	PIAL	2118	242	O	4	0	1	6	0	2	10
2	Large tree	PIAL	2347	290	U	15	0	0	0	3	1	0
2	Large tree	PIAL	2347	290	U	15	0	0	0	3	1	0
2	Large tree	PIAL	2268	222	D	52	0	0	0	1	0	0
1	Large tree	PIAL	2460	209	E	86	0	0	0	2	0	0
3	Large tree	PIAL	2256	202	V	34	0	0	0	9	0	5
3	Large tree	PIAL	2256	202	V	34	0	0	0	9	0	5
3	Large tree	PIAL	2256	202	V	34	0	0	0	9	0	5
<u>3</u>	Large tree	PIAL	2387	221	V	35	0	0	0	3	3	9
<u>4</u>	Large tree	PIAL	2128	278	Z	4	0	0	0	1	1	0
1	Large tree	PIAL	2134	201	D	48	0	0	0	1	0	0
<u>4</u>	Large tree	PIAL	2975	247	W	80	0	0	0	26	4	0
3	Large tree	PIAL	2914	234	N	3	0	0	0	2	0	8
1	Large tree	PIAL	2390	267	Q	9	0	0	0	2	1	10
1	Unknown	PIAL	2079	166	U	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	Unknown	PIAL	1939	167	U	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	Unknown	PIAL	2524	182	D	45	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	Unknown	PIAL	2237	256	D	57	0	0	0	1	0	0
3	Unknown	PIAL	2335	181	I	22	0	0	0	0	0	6
1	Unknown	PIAL	2390	236	E	90	0	0	0	0	0	1
1	Unknown	PIAL	1783	190	A	50	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	Unknown	PIAL	2076	236	A	75	0	0	0	0	0	0
<u>2</u>	Unknown	PIAL	1896	220	S	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
<u>2</u>	Unknown	<i>PIFL</i>	2518	228	S	3	3	0	0	0	0	0

¹ Numbers in bold italics with underline indicate samples from plots with lab-identified samples of both species.

² PIAL = *Pinus albicaulis*; PIFL = *Pinus flexilis*

³Our analysis was based on actual plot elevation, which cannot be publicly released. Elevations presented in this table are the publicly available values based on approximate plot coordinates. See Burrill et al. 2023 (Sections 2.4.20 – 2.4.22, SURVEY.RSCD = 22) for more details.

⁴ Unique letter for each crew lead follow those used in Figure 3.

⁵ Crew leader experience is the count of FIA plots in the study area with whitebark pine and/or limber pine present that a crew leader had measured at the time of sample collection (including the plot from which the sample was taken).